

A New Ecosystem of Early Music Studies

Historical Musicology in European Higher Music Education Institutions: Institutional Frameworks, Curricula, Research, and Future Perspectives

Edited by Aleksandra Pister & Philippe Vendrix

Contributors: Gareth Balch, Augustin Braud, David Burn, Sergio Cerrillo, Ivan Ćurković, Ferran Escrivà-Llorca, Stefan Gasch, Gabriele Groll, Maciej Jochymczyk, Magdalini Kalopana, Stella Kourmpa, Christophe Levaux, Eliona Lici, Stefano Lorenzetti, Angel Manuel Olmos, Mimi Mitchell, Oleksandr Okhrimenko, Ivana Perković, Aleksandra Pister, Nevin Şahin, Thomas Schmidt, Marianna Siatkowska, Pedro Sousa Silva, Dimonsthenis Spanoudakis, Petros Stergiopoulos, Philippe Vendrix, Adam Whittaker, Rebecca Wolf.

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1. Introduction

This report examines the role, evolution, and current status of historical musicology within European Higher Music Education Institutions, henceforth referred to as HMEIs, in line with the terminology used by The Association Européenne des Conservatoires, Académies de Musique et Musikhochschulen (AEC).¹ HMEIs include institutions commonly referred to as conservatoires, music academies, or colleges of music. The present report complements the first report on historical musicology in the university sector published in 2025.² Drawing on extensive research from across Europe, it explores the complex institutional settings, pedagogical models, and research capabilities that characterize historical musicology in these specialised educational environments. The findings reveal considerable diversity in how historical musicology has been integrated into HMEIs programs over time, with significant variations in curriculum design, research support, and faculty qualifications across different national contexts. While HMEIs have generally emphasised performance training alongside, for instance, composition or conducting, historical musicology has increasingly been recognized as an essential component of a comprehensive musical education, albeit with implementation approaches that often differ markedly from university models.

Historical musicology is represented in virtually all HMEIs across Europe but with considerable variation in its conceptualisation and delivery model. In order to summarise and articulate the different ways in which this happens, and to understand how this informs the status of the discipline in practical terms, we first need to establish practical definitions of "historical musicology", and to clarify more precisely what is encompassed by the notion of HMEIs. Institutional models are remarkably diverse, for historical and national reasons; this variety needs to be addressed. As a consequence, the embedding of historical musicology in their curricula, as well as the content and structure of these curricula, is just as varied.

1.1. Defining historical musicology in HMEIs

Across Europe, there is substantial variation in how historical musicology is defined, implemented, and valued within HMEIs. A fundamental question concerns how narrowly "historical musicology" should be defined, and in particular whether it should be distinguished from "music history" and "music theory" within the taught curriculum. For practical purposes and with the aim of adopting an inclusive approach, historical musicology is understood here as any activity involving high-level intellectual

¹ The **Association Européenne des Conservatoires, Académies de Musique et Musikhochschulen (AEC)** is the European association representing higher music education institutions, promoting quality, diversity, and international cooperation in artistic training. <https://aec-music.eu/> [accessed: 29.05.2025].

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14621706> [accessed: 29.05.2025].

engagement with music history. This definition thus allows for the integration of historical inquiry with performance practice, a hallmark of education in HMEIs across the continent.

The presence of a dedicated musicology department within HMEIs often serves as an indicator of the value placed on historical musicology within these institutions. This structural approach varies significantly across Europe: in Serbia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, Bulgaria, Spain, Ukraine and some other countries, some HMEIs maintain distinct musicology departments. In the UK, such content is usually integrated within broader "academic studies" departments or increasingly within the remit of 'professional development' curriculum strands. In Germany, the organisational structures vary considerably between institutions. Musicology at German HMEIs (*Hochschule für Musik*) is a cross-sectional subject: students of all music-related subjects (BA, MA, teacher training) must take courses in music history. Nevertheless, there are also a considerable number of HMEIs that have their own musicology department. This diversity of structures reflects different national traditions, institutional histories, and educational philosophies. In some cases, the domain of historical musicology in HMEIs has been gradually subsumed under a general theory area, encompassing subjects such as ear training, analysis, and acoustics, and repositioned primarily as curricular support for practice-based programmes.

Case Study: Historical Musicology Teaching in Greece

Reaching a deeper understanding of the current landscape through the lens of Historical Musicology education in Greece requires an analysis of the broader corpus of studies defining the performing arts. This is because the teaching of music history is an integral part of those studies. The evolution of so-called "Conservatory studies" in Greece necessitates a qualitative distinction between institutions that have historically covered—and continue to comprehensively cover—the entire spectrum of educational domains governing higher-level education in music performance (Performing Arts practice), and those that, for reasons outside the scope of this study, do not. The foundational concept of the term *Odeion* (Conservatory), as stated in the founding declaration of the Athens Conservatoire and especially in the curriculum implemented therein, highlights the need for comprehensive coverage of all academic domains that define music as a performing art. This was addressed by establishing specialised schools within the Conservatoire's structure, each supervised by an administrative board (*Euphor*) for the Schools of Percussion, Wind Instruments, and Strings. After the foundation of Music Studies departments in Universities, graduates of Musicology, including those specialised in Historical Musicology, may be appointed to teach theoretical subjects at a Conservatory without holding a Conservatory degree as a strict prerequisite.

In this framework, the School of Theoretical Studies within a Conservatoire includes the study of Music History in addition to courses in Music Theory and Advanced Music Theory subjects. This theoretical education directly relates to the discipline of Historical Musicology and includes courses in Music History, Musical Morphology, and Organology. These subjects are taught in Greece as part of the curriculum

initially designed and implemented at the Athens Conservatoire, and subsequently incorporated into the series of state laws governing the instruction of these subjects since that time.

1.2. Defining HMEIs in higher education

A defining characteristic of HMEIs is their predominant focus on practical musical training, which can be informed by historical musicological research. These specialist institutions typically do not encompass the full range of faculties found in universities. They generally comprise one or a small number of departments focused on practice-related activities/arts, music or performing arts. In many countries, HMEIs operate as institutions independent from universities, while in others, they function as components of universities or (for example in some cases in the UK) as semi-independent faculties of broad-based universities.³

It is important to mention that not all institutions labelled “conservatoires” or “conservatories” are fully integrated into higher education systems, defined as institutions of tertiary-level specialist learning and research. This ambiguous status has created challenges in several countries, particularly regarding the recognition of conservatory qualifications within broader higher education frameworks. For instance, in Greece, a legal distinction between public and private conservatories has significantly impacted their recognition status in higher education. In some countries, a clear distinction is made between pre-college conservatories – such as *conservatorios profesionales* in Spain or *conservatoires régionaux* in France – and higher-level institutions, often labelled *conservatorios superiores* or *conservatoires supérieurs*. By contrast, in places like Portugal and Hungary, the term conservatory refers exclusively to pre-college music education. Elsewhere, including Albania, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Poland, Serbia, or Romania, “academies/faculties of music” are considered to be equivalent to “conservatories” in higher education. Nevertheless, as in the case of the Athens Conservatoire, they can be associated with a university. While these institutions include a core emphasis on performance training, they maintain a broader profile. Musicological research, which often includes ethnomusicology, music theory, and music education, is an equally important area of academic activity. These faculties are sometimes affiliated with universities, which can help them to develop comprehensive academic programs and research agendas that extend beyond the performance-focused conservatory model.

³ In the UK, for example, the Royal Birmingham Conservatoire is an Associate Faculty of Birmingham City University. In Wales, the Royal Welsh Conservatoire of Music and Drama is an autonomous part of the University of South Wales. The London College of Music (HMEI) is part of the University of West London.

Case Study: Music Academies in Ukraine

Following the educational reforms of the 1990s and early 2000s, conservatories in Ukraine were transformed into music academies and granted university-level status, starting with the establishment by Presidential decree of the Ukrainian National Tchaikovsky Academy of Music in 1995. This transformation elevated seven major music institutions, including those in Kyiv, Lviv, Odessa, and Kharkiv, providing a university-like framework of faculties and specialised departments that allowed them to offer comprehensive academic programs at bachelor, masters, and doctoral levels. Unlike standard higher education institutions, Ukrainian music academies operate under a distinctive dual subordination structure. The Ministry of Culture provides primary administrative oversight, while the Ministry of Education and Science establishes educational standards and degree requirements. This dual governance system creates a balance where music academies maintain both artistic excellence and academic rigour, positioning them as key cultural and educational institutions that combine specialised artistic focus with rigorous academic standards.

2. Institutional framework

2.1. Diverse institutional models

European HMEIs demonstrate remarkable diversity in their institutional models, reflecting different national traditions and historical developments. The relationship between historical musicology and HMEI education has evolved distinctly in different European contexts. In many Eastern European countries, such as Serbia and Croatia, HMEIs often mirror university structures or are constituent parts of universities, with dedicated departments for historical musicology. At the University of Arts Belgrade, for example, faculty workloads typically allocate half of an academic member's time for research and half for teaching, reflecting a strong commitment to scholarly activities as an integral part of the institutional model. However, in Croatia this percentage can increase or decrease according to the availability of staff and/or resources; musicologists often do more teaching than research, hindering their advancement as researchers.

In Western Europe, there is a wide range of institutional models. On the one hand, in the UK, HMEIs generally do not maintain separate musicology departments but instead integrate historical studies into broader "academic studies" curricula. In contrast, in Germany, France and Italy, as further examples, some institutions maintain distinct musicology departments whilst others adopt more integrated approaches.

Case Studies: Institutional Models and Recognition Frameworks in European HMEIs

In **Greece**, the distinction between public and private conservatories has created unique challenges. The Athens Conservatoire (founded in 1871) and the State Conservatory of Thessaloniki (founded in 1914)

share similar structures but have different legal statuses; the former remains in the private sector while the latter is publicly funded. This legal distinction has significant implications for their recognition within the country's higher education framework, as Article 16 of the 1974 Constitution secured the privilege of providing higher education exclusively to public-sector institutions. In the context of music studies in Greece, this constitutional limitation creates a long-standing institutional barrier that severely undermines the equivalence and international standing of Greek conservatories when compared with their European counterparts, many of which —regardless of legal status— are fully recognized within national higher education systems.

A similar problem happens in **France** with the *École Normale Cortot*, which was founded in 1919 to welcome the foreign students who would not be admitted to the *Conservatoire de Paris*. It is then no surprise that it is based on a very similar model to the CNSMDP (*Conservatoire National Supérieur de Musique et de Danse de Paris*) while sometimes even sharing professors. While a private music academy, it draws on a public model and offers musicology classes by fully fledged professors holding CNSM prizes and PhDs.

In **Portugal**, a reform in the 1980s restructured music education by creating polytechnic schools such as ESML and ESMAE, which inherited the HMEIs' role in professional music training and began awarding recognised degrees in performance, composition, and related fields. At the same time, musicology was assigned to the university sector, with NOVA University Lisbon establishing the first dedicated programme. This created a functional distinction: polytechnics focused on artistic practice, while universities specialised in research-based musicology. From the 1990s onward, this divide began to blur as universities like Aveiro, Évora, and Minho launched programmes that included performance and composition. While musicology has remained within the university system, the boundaries between academic and artistic training have become increasingly porous.

In **Ukraine**, the National Academy of Music in Kyiv, commonly known as Kyiv Conservatory, functions with a university-like structure comprising three faculties and multiple specialised departments. Within this organizational framework, historical musicology is primarily handled through dedicated departments including the Department of Ukrainian Music History and Musical Folklore, the Department of World Music History, and the Department of Early Music (which was founded by Nina Gerasymova-Persydska in 2000). These specialised units offer comprehensive programs at bachelor, master's, and doctoral levels, with research focusing on Byzantine musical traditions, Ukrainian church monody, and particularly baroque *partesny* (part-song) concerts.

2.2. Academic staff and qualifications

In terms of staffing, virtually all HMEIs employ academics whose role is exclusively or primarily that of a musicologist. However, their status varies greatly. Many institutions (usually the ones that place a greater emphasis on musicological research and musicology in the curriculum) employ a number of musicologists on full-time permanent contracts, often as professors, or on temporary contracts. Both of these staff are expected to carry out research, and their teaching load reflects the expectation that they will be active researchers. Such researchers are typically

required or expected to hold doctorates (PhDs), and, in some countries, also the “Habilitation.”⁴

A second group of academic and artistic staff at HMEIs comprises the representatives of the academic mid-level faculty (*Akademischer Mittelbau*). This includes examined or graduate academic personnel who do not hold a professorship. This category encompasses so-called “mid-level professorships” (*Assistenzprofessuren*), namely associate professors, as well as staff from third-party-funded research projects who can be recruited for teaching. These researchers may hold temporary, fixed-term contracts and permanent positions. Historical musicologists may also be employed in other parts of HMEIs (such as in libraries or archives), contributing to the research culture of the institution, and sometimes its teaching, even where this is not their primary role.

There are national differences in career development and mobility, in particular concerning the possibility of moving between HMEIs and universities as part of standard career progression. Such differences can have far-reaching consequences on salaries, as well as the stability or fragility of the positions involved.

2.3. Required qualifications across Europe

The qualifications required for teaching historical musicology in European HMEIs vary considerably across national contexts, reflecting different traditions and institutional arrangements. While a master's degree in musicology or a related field is typically the minimum requirement, many institutions favour candidates with doctoral qualifications, or indeed require that qualification outright. A critical mass of the COST countries' higher education systems was involved in the Bologna processes, which aimed to create a common European Higher Education Area (EHEA) including a common degree system among the participating countries. However, these processes did not include the unification of formal requirements for teaching positions. The requirements can therefore differ drastically across the European higher-education landscape, both in the statutory frameworks and sector practices. A few examples help illustrate this variation.

2.3.1. ALBANIA

In Albania, becoming a professional musicologist generally requires a strong background in performance, typically advanced studies in an instrument like piano or violin, bachelor's degree in musicology or a related field from a recognized university, with master's and doctoral degrees necessary for higher-level academic or research careers. The Faculty of Music at the University of Arts in Tirana is the primary institution,

⁴ Habilitation is a post-doctoral qualification or academic process required in many European countries. For example, in German-speaking countries, the journey to a professorship in musicology at a conservatory usually parallels that of a professorship at a university, requiring a habilitation (or equivalent) following a doctorate (Dr. phil.).

initially modelled on the Soviet system, combining theory and practical training with ideological content. A 5-year BA-MA program is standard, with theses supervised by PhD staff. Pursuing a PhD involves original research focusing on Albanian or international music topics. The faculty established postgraduate programs in 2005, including Master's and doctoral cycles. The curriculum emphasizes music history, harmony, ethnomusicology, and research skills to prepare specialists for academia, cultural preservation, and artistic development. Master's thesis can only be supervised by teaching staff with PhDs in Musicology.

2.3.2. CROATIA

In Croatia, apart from the University of Zagreb Academy of Music, musicologists also teach at academies of music housed likewise at universities (Split, Osijek and Pula), but their teaching is narrowed down mostly to music history overview courses. The careers of all these people, like the career of every member of the academic community in Croatia, is regulated in a specific professional field. For musicians this is the field of music, for musicologists it is the field of humanities. As such, the employee of each of the four institutions mentioned needs to develop their career according to the standards of the field in question. As a result, people can start teaching musicological courses (including history of music overview courses) without a PhD as an assistant or lecturer under the supervision of a professor, but in order to become fully independent, they all need to acquire a PhD in musicology or on a musicological topic.

2.3.3. FRANCE

In France, while a master's degree is mandatory for teaching historical musicology in HMEIs, candidates with PhDs enjoy an advantage when applying for positions in larger institutions such as the national conservatories of Paris and Lyon (CNSMD) or other regional HMEIs. Interestingly, the preferred degree for these positions is often the state diploma in music teaching awarded by HMEIs rather than university degrees, highlighting a structural issue in the professional pathways available to young musicologists.

2.3.4. GERMANY AND AUSTRIA

In German-speaking countries, the path to a professorship in musicology at an HMEI usually parallels that of a professorship at a university. It requests a Habilitation (or equivalent) following a doctorate (Dr. phil.). Therefore, it is possible to switch from an HMEI to a university and vice versa, allowing for a flexible career development. Academics usually start teaching on semester-based teaching contracts (*Lehrauftrag*) when they have completed their PhD, but increasingly also as doctoral students. Federal states are running both the HMEIs and the universities. A similar model is followed in Poland, Serbia and Croatia is similar: one can switch from HMEIs to a university, but the principle difference is the Habilitation which is not required.

2.3.5. GREECE

In Greece, there are two qualifications that are required for teaching Historical Musicology in HMEIs. The *Ptychion* is an HMEI qualification, representing junior academic qualification. The second is the *Diploma*, which includes both performance and teaching and is considered to be equivalent to a bachelor's degree from a university. A Master's or PhD is of course appreciated as an additional qualification. HMEIs confer the *Ptychion* and *Diploma* degrees, which are recognized by the Ministry of Culture, however, currently they have not yet been formally aligned with the European Qualification Framework. Positions within HMEIs are not permanent. In practice, salaries are calculated on the basis of hours completed and remain stable even though contracts are not open-ended.

2.3.6. ITALY

In Italy, the minimum required qualification to teach historical musicology at HMEIs is a Master's degree in musicology. Although a PhD is not formally required, it is increasingly common among successful candidates, reflecting a gradual shift towards higher academic standards more closely aligned with those of universities.

This trend coincides with significant institutional developments. During the 2023–2024 academic year, approximately fifty professors of music history were appointed in Italian conservatories. That same year, these institutions—formally recognised as higher education institutions under the AFAM system—were, for the first time, authorised to offer accredited doctoral programmes. While most of these programmes focus on artistic research, a number of leading conservatories (e.g., Conservatorio “Giuseppe Verdi” in Milan, Conservatorio “Santa Cecilia” in Rome) have introduced doctoral curricula that include historical musicology and music theory as core academic components⁵.

These developments reflect a progressive alignment with the Bologna Process, fully integrating HMEIs degrees into the three-cycle structure (Bachelor–Master–Doctorate) and the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS). The increasing presence of PhD-qualified staff and the growing involvement of Italian HMEIs in Erasmus+ programmes and EU-funded research projects indicate a consolidation of HMEIs as academic institutions with research capacity and enhanced international collaboration.

2.3.7. POLAND

In Poland, the situation is complex due to the existence of two parallel educational paths: university musicology departments and music theory departments within music academies (HMEIs). Historically, academic staff responsible for teaching music history

⁵ https://www.consmi.it/it/1363/ambiti-di-ricerca?utm_source=chatgpt.com;
https://conservatoriosantacecilia.it/dottorato-di-ricerca-in-scienze-e-culture-del-patrimonio-musicale/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

in Polish music academies often had some musicological background, typically at the doctoral level. However, this pattern has changed in recent years as Polish music academies gained authority to award doctoral degrees (DMA equivalent). Consequently, music history in these institutions is increasingly taught by music theorists rather than specialised musicologists. However music theorists (holding a DMA degree equivalent) typically are not hired by universities (the exceptions are short-term contracts for lectures on contemporary music, music acoustics, jazz music, etc.). This apparent separation between these two models of institution is justified by the specificity of the curricula of both education paths.

2.3.8. PORTUGAL

In Portugal, HMEIs Portugal's public music schools—such as ESML in Lisbon and ESMAE in Porto—are required to comply with national regulations concerning faculty qualifications, which have become increasingly stringent since the Bologna reform. Over the past 15 years, this has led to a significant increase in the number of faculty members holding doctoral degrees. At ESMAE, for example, approximately half of the full-time academic staff now hold a PhD. However, not all of these doctorates are in musicology, and only a subset of PhD holders actively engage in formalised research, although it is not a contractual requirement. Importantly, higher education institutions in Portugal enjoy autonomy in defining the academic and professional profiles of the staff they wish to recruit. Including the type of doctoral training they consider appropriate. When hiring in theoretical areas, music schools often favour candidates capable of covering a broad range of subjects such as music theory and analysis, music history, and music pedagogy. As a result, while the academic qualification of HMEIs staff has improved markedly, research in historical musicology within these institutions remains uneven and often dependent on individual initiative rather than institutional research agendas.

2.3.9. SPAIN

Spain's regulatory framework for accessing teaching positions in HMEIs has progressively aligned with European standards, particularly those of Italy. Since 2019, candidates must hold a research-oriented Master's degree to be eligible for public competitive examinations (*oposiciones*). However, between the late 1980s and this reform, no nationwide examinations were held. Recruitment was delegated to regional governments (*autonomous communities*), which applied disparate criteria, resulting in a non-homogeneous system among HMEIs. Consequently, many interim professors remained in post for 15 to 20 years, while tenured faculty retired without systematic replacement.

This prolonged reliance on interim staff raised concerns at the European level regarding employment stability and compliance with Directive 1999/70/EC on fixed-term work. In response, Spanish authorities launched an extraordinary regularisation process in 2023, granting permanent positions to most interim professors without

requiring them to pass competitive exams. As many of these appointments predated the 2019 reform, a significant portion of the regularised faculty do not meet the current academic qualification standards, particularly the requirement of a Master's degree.

The recently enacted Law 1/2024 introduces a new academic career structure for higher artistic education. It stipulates that access to permanent full professorships now requires a doctoral degree, replacing the former category of *Catedrático de Música y Artes Escénicas*, which did not mandate a PhD. A transitional provision allows current holders to retain their status and salary or apply for reclassification under the new title (*Catedrático de Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores*) upon obtaining a doctorate within ten years. However, as the law permits incumbents to remain in post without meeting this requirement, the incentive to pursue doctoral studies remains limited. Moreover, since competencies in education are devolved, the effective implementation of the law will depend on each regional government's regulatory development.

2.3.10. TÜRKIYE

In Türkiye, because all HMEIs were connected to universities with a decree-law in 1982, artist-instructor positions gradually disappeared and the minimum requirement for undergraduate-level teaching to date is an MA degree. Although musicology has been in the academic agenda since the late 19th century, the academic organization of historical musicology has not yet been specified as a distinct field. The only historical musicology MA program in Türkiye requires a PhD (or DMA equivalent) degree for teaching, but the discipline is not specified, the current faculty has degrees ranging from a DMA in piano to a PhD in theology. In addition to the 20 undergraduate programmes in musicology throughout the country, there are graduate programmes in a variety of disciplines (music theory, history, art history, Islamic art, Turkish literature, etc.), in which a focus on historical musicology is possible, building interdisciplinarity into the very structure of the field.

2.3.11. UKRAINE

In Ukraine, musicologists teaching at HMEIs must meet qualification requirements that are uniformly applied across all higher education institutions, as regulated by identical legislative acts of Ukraine and the Ministry of Education and Science. The academic career ladder consists of three main levels: Assistant (entry-level position requiring at least a Master's degree and showing scholarly potential), Associate Professor (Docent, requiring a PhD/Candidate of Sciences degree and published research), and Full Professor (requiring a Doctor of Sciences degree, significant research contributions, and extensive teaching experience). For the music field specifically, the conferment of Associate Professor or Professor titles also requires extensive concert activity, archived audio and video recordings, and recognition as a laureate of international competitions and festivals. Each position demands progressively higher qualifications in both academic achievement and pedagogical experience, with promotions based

on a combination of research output, artistic achievements, and peer recognition. These qualifications are governed by standardized national frameworks that ensure consistency across all disciplines in higher education institutions.

2.3.12. UNITED KINGDOM

In the UK, there is more an established practice than a legal framework for career progression and for appointments to posts that involve teaching historical musicology. HMEIs are in this respect no different from universities; a candidate would be expected to have a PhD and established research and publication in aspects of historical musicology, demonstrating leadership within a field. The progression is typically through Lectureship, Senior Lectureship, Readerships, and Professorial roles. Movement for historical musicologists between universities and HMEIs is not prescribed by law as in Italy; it will depend much more on the specialist interests of the institution concerned and on how an individual musicologist may be able to contribute to teaching and research.

2.4. Comparative data of some employment criteria for historical musicology academic staff in European HMEIs

The methodological approach for the collection of the data presented below combines open-access legislative sources and expert input from members of the COST Action *EarlyMuse*. The countries represented correspond to those for which verified data was available, or where data and information was contributed by national experts involved in the Action. The more significant presence of certain countries within the network has facilitated more comprehensive data collection for those national contexts.

The table provides a comparative overview of the minimum academic qualifications required for teaching in HMEIs across the countries represented. It outlines the qualifications established by national legislation for teaching at BA and MA levels, doctoral supervision, the requirement of a PhD or habilitation, and the recognition of artistic output. The information reflects current legal and regulatory frameworks, with some exceptions addressed in the following lines.

Based on this table, 12 countries require a Master degree for teaching at the undergraduate level. 3 countries –Albania, Austria, Portugal– require a PhD qualification for teaching at undergraduate level. The qualifications required to teach at the MA level in HMEIs vary significantly across countries. In eight countries (Spain, Germany, Italy, Croatia, Lithuania, Poland, France and Belgium), a Master's degree is sufficient, while in seven others (Türkiye, Portugal, UK, Ukraine, Austria, Albania, Serbia), a PhD is required for the same teaching level. For the Netherlands and Greece, no specific data is available, which may suggest that the requirements are either not clearly defined or not uniformly applied.

In terms of the qualifications for PhD supervision, the data shows that the majority of HMEIs do not award a PhD in musicology, rather a doctorate of Arts or in artistic research. Most of the PhDs offered in HMEIs are also mostly oriented towards artistic research, but there are a small number of HMEIs that award a PhD in musicology in cooperation with a university or/and research institution, f.i. in Lithuania, Switzerland (Schola Cantorum Basiliensis). In Italy, a PhD degree is preferred but not mandatory. 7 countries require a PhD degree (Albania, Belgium, Croatia, Lithuania, Portugal, UK, Ukraine), and 6 countries require a PhD + some kind of additional qualification, such as habilitation, research track record, and professorship (Germany, Poland, Serbia, Türkiye, Albania, Austria).

Regarding the requirement of a doctoral degree (PhD) for tenured positions, 10 represented countries mandate it for access to teaching posts in HMEIs. The majority of the countries do not require habilitation, except Germany, Italy, Poland, Türkiye. So this kind of requirement is in significant minority according to most of the educational systems across Europe. Still in order to proceed in an academic career one must fulfil the requirements that are similar to habilitation, e.g. to publish a monograph.

As shown in the table, artistic output is officially recognised as a qualification for teaching in HMEIs in 9 countries. In 7 other countries, while it is not formally required, it is still considered desirable, for example Portugal, Italy, and UK.

Some countries are moving toward stricter qualification frameworks, for example in Spain, the latest legislation (Law 1/2024) will require a PhD to obtain the rank of *Catedrático* (Full Professor) at a *Conservatorio Superior* (Higher Conservatory) once fully implemented. In the UK the professionalisation of the discipline and sector, and the desire of HMEIs to raise their status and credibility as research institutions, has resulted in a de facto requirement of a doctorate for permanent academic positions.

The notes in the table indicate that in some countries, such as Germany and Austria, qualification requirements are standardised across all higher education institutions, including both HMEIs and universities. In contrast, other countries, like Spain, do not have unified requirements, which limits the possibility of moving between institutions within the Higher Education sector.

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
Albania	PhD	PhD	PhD*	Yes	No*	Yes	In Albania, the qualification system is standardised across all higher education

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
							institutions and the Ministry of Education and Sports regulations. The professors for the academic positions of teaching require academic qualifications and artistic achievements. * Doctor of Sciences degree serves similar function for full professors positions
Austria	PhD	PhD	Professorship (with/without Habilitation)	Yes	No	No	Formal academic track
Belgium	MA	MA	PhD	No	No	Yes	
Croatia	MA	MA	PhD	Yes	No (habilitation does not exist)	No	When choosing a career path, one is either in the field of humanities (musicology) or performing arts (music), it is not possible to switch or to have the output from the other field recognised for either employment or professional advancement.

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
France	MA	MA	Not applicable	No	No	No*	<p>* not formally but background in artistic practice considered desirable</p> <p>Only conservatories in Paris and Lyon offer doctorates in collaboration with universities, which provide the scientific support.</p>
Germany	MA	MA	PhD + Habilitation	Yes	Yes*	No	* habilitation required for full professorship, Highly formal academic track.
Greece	Conservatory Degree (Bachelor or Diploma) or BA in Musicology						Conservatories and universities have no official institutional relevance
Italy	MA	MA	No*	No	Yes	Yes	*PhD is preferred but not mandatory+Tenured position. All the professors recently recruited have a PhD in Musicology or related disciplines
Lithuania	MA	MA	PhD	No	No	Yes	

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
Netherlands					No	Yes	
Poland	MA	MA	PhD/DMA + Habilitation*	Yes	Yes	No	*It is possible to be an assistant supervisor having only a doctorate without a habilitation
Portugal	PhD or Specialist Title	PhD or Specialist Title	PhD	Yes	No (just for career progression)	Yes	
Serbia	MA (for assistant - students on PhD studies), PhD for all other teaching staff	PhD	PhD + official requirements for supervision defined by the Law (number of articles, monographs, qualitative work)	Yes	No	No	50% research, 50% teaching in workload
Spain	MA	MA	Not applicable	Yes**	No	Yes	* PhD will be required once the Law 1/2024 is fully applied for both BA and MA teaching
Türkiye	MA	PhD (or DMA equivalent)	PhD (or DMA equivalent) + completed supervision of MA	Yes	Depending on the academic track (assistant professors)	Yes	All conservatories under universities, university regulations apply, universities without conservatories have faculties of fine arts

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
					expected to complete habilitation or their position is transferred to instructor)		and design with a similar status to conservatories
UK	MA	Doctorate	Doctorate	Yes	No	No*	<p>*not formally but background in artistic practice is often considered desirable</p> <p>Qualifications not governed by statute, so every institution (university or conservatory) can define their own requirements, within the very broad subject benchmark statements by the UK Qualifications Authority (Ofqual). But the professionalisation of the discipline and sector, and the desire of conservatories to raise their status and credibility as research institutions, has resulted in a de facto requirement of a</p>

Country	Minimum Qualification for BA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for MA Teaching	Minimum Qualification for PhD Supervision	Doctorate Required?	Habilitation Required?	Artistic Output Recognized?	Notes
							doctorate for permanent academic positions
Ukraine	MA	PhD	PhD	Yes, for higher positions (Associate Professor and Professor); not mandatory for Assistant positions	No	Yes	Teaching positions combine requirements for both academic qualifications and artistic achievements, with the latter being particularly important in conservatories and music academies.

2.5. Academic career paths and research expectations

Academic career paths and research expectations for historical musicologists working in HMEIs vary across European countries. In many cases, these expectations differ from those placed on performance faculty within the same institutions, and also differ from those placed on historical musicologists working in university contexts. These differences concern not only the expectations of the positions, but may also be reflected in differences of salary. There may also be differences in how staff are assessed, and the impacts these have on career progression opportunities. This subsection provides examples of the different academic pathway models in different European countries.

In Serbia, for instance, the University of Arts Belgrade models its faculty workload structure after universities, with approximately half of an academic member's time reserved for research and half for teaching. This approach recognises and supports the scholarly dimension of musicological work within the HMEI context. However, since March 2025, the Serbian government changed this ratio: the teaching workload norm for academic staff was increased from 20 to 35 hours per week, while the norm allocated for scientific research or artistic work was reduced from 20 to 5 hours per week. Assistant positions are held by doctoral students and are typically awarded for a period of 3 years, renewable once. Positions such as assistant professor and

associate professor are appointed for 5-year terms, with the possibility of reappointment. Only full professors receive permanent contracts (tenured positions), following a national procedure that evaluates research, teaching, and institutional contributions. All academic staff sign individual employment contracts and may, with institutional approval, be employed by another higher education institution for up to 30% of full-time engagement. The requirement to award doctoral degrees has become a precondition for recognition as a higher education institution in some contexts, as exemplified by the foundation of the University of the Arts in Serbia, which includes Musicology as a component.

In Croatia, a similar division of workload applies: 40% teaching, 40% research and 10% administration. However, in practice these ratios are fluid, since in the case of insufficient staff or funding, the teaching workload often increases and research activities suffer. As far as the professional advancement is concerned (from assistant and associate to full professor), musicologists employed at Croatian music academies have to do the same as the ones employed at universities: they need to publish, participate in research projects etc. to advance their career.

In the UK, expectations vary considerably between institutions. Two of the nine HMEIs, generally understood as conservatories, do not offer doctoral-level education, limiting research opportunities and expectations for faculty. However, the broader trend in British conservatories has been toward greater research engagement, with institutions like the Royal Academy of Music joining the University of London federation (1999) and others securing their own degree-awarding powers, all of which embed mandatory research components for their staff. In terms of career progression, academic staff at universities and conservatories are in principle subject to the same salary spine negotiated with the trade unions (most conservatories participating in the same Higher Education collective bargaining process with universities), but professorial salaries are freely negotiable above the “professorial minimum” although many universities have higher starting salaries for their academic staff. In practice, salaries for full professors in conservatories tend to be somewhat lower on average than for professors of music(ology) in universities, especially the more prestigious ones.

Belgium and the German-speaking countries represent a system in transition, with more HMEIs now offering PhDs and artistic doctorates that include musicological elements co-supervised by musicology staff. Historical musicologists employed in HMEIs may hold various positions beyond teaching, working in libraries, archives, and research centres affiliated with these institutions. The expectations placed on musicology staff vary widely. They may be employed as full-time academic faculty with research expectations reflected in their teaching loads, or alternatively, music history may be delivered by staff who are principally or entirely employed as teachers with no research expectations and correspondingly higher teaching commitments.

In German and Austrian HMEIs there is often a disparity between permanent professorships and non-staff or freelance lecturers. The latter includes staff from third-

party research projects. While up to around 20 percent of courses at universities generally, and between around 25 and 50 percent at universities of applied sciences, are taught by non-staff lecturers, this proportion is sometimes more than around 60 or even 70 percent at German conservatories. Non-staff lecturers at conservatoires are not merely employed to supplement the teaching offer; they cover a substantial part of the teaching capacity. In the coming years, this disparity will inevitably lead to increasing political battles over the distribution of teaching staff. A consequence of this is likely to be the departure of lecturers in historical musicology and the transfer of tasks to full time professors and academics with permanent posts in historical musicology, in turn leading to a decrease in diversity. Due to the 2021 amendment to the Universities Act, which imposes a rigid time limit on the employment of externally funded staff at academic institutions, the teaching engagement of non-tenured academic mid-level faculty in Austria has significantly decreased already.

In the Netherlands, there are historical musicologists as a permanent part of the HMEIs staff. With more academic requirements expected of the students, an increase in musicological staff will be necessary. Where appointed, these faculty members are often employed on a yearly contract for a limited number of hours, creating an insecure situation for many on the staff. After two years (for a larger number of hours) or four, a contract must be offered.

In Türkiye, HMEIs professors in public institutions are appointed permanently after their habilitation. In contrast, private universities follow more diverse procedures regarding faculty appointments, depending on their internal regulations. Professors have a standard teaching workload of up to 30 hours per week. Research is encouraged at all academic levels, from research assistants to full professors, but its recognition depends on the academic rank of the individual. Teaching obligations are fixed and cannot be reduced or substituted by research activities.

Across Portugal, higher music education institutions—both polytechnic schools and university departments—have adopted varied strategies for hiring musicologists, particularly in the area of historical musicology. In some institutions, music history and related subjects are taught by faculty staff whose primary training is in performance or composition, reflecting a preference for a variety of teaching profiles. Elsewhere, musicology is embedded within broader theory departments, where hiring favours candidates capable of covering a spectrum of areas such as analysis, ear training, aesthetics, and research methods. A smaller number of institutions maintain dedicated musicologists with doctoral qualifications, often as a result of recruitment practices from the 1990s and early 2000s, when PhD holders—mostly in musicology—had a distinct advantage in academic hiring. Career progression in both university and polytechnic systems is structured in parallel but with distinct tracks, with different titles: Assistant, Associate, and Full Professor in universities, and Adjunct, Coordinating, and

Principal Coordinating Professor in polytechnics. While initial salary levels⁶ in polytechnics tend to be lower, especially at the entry level, the two systems become fully aligned in terms of remuneration and expectations at senior levels. Teaching loads also differ: university faculty staff typically teach between 240 and 300 hours annually, while polytechnic staff are expected to teach between 300 and 360 hours. Expectations around research vary according to institutional missions and culture, as each school has autonomy to define its own evaluation criteria. However, research output—not necessarily in musicology—is increasingly valued in performance management reviews, and affiliation with accredited research centres is becoming essential. Since research funding is awarded to these centres and not directly to the schools, institutional faculties are increasingly incentivised to pursue active research agendas. Recent legislative changes allowing polytechnics to award of doctoral degrees have further encouraged this shift, reinforcing the role of research in academic careers and accelerating the structural convergence of the two subsystems. Several polytechnic institutes have already begun the process of transitioning into Polytechnic Universities, signalling a shift towards complete structural alignment across the sector.

In Spain, there is no structured career progression for professors working in HMEIs. Once a person is appointed to a professorship, there are no higher positions to be promoted to. Salary increases are automatic: every three years, professors receive a pay raise (*trienios*), and every six years they can earn an additional raise by completing certain general training courses. However, these courses—amounting to 10 credits over six years—are often not relevant to higher artistic education. Although research is officially encouraged, in practice there is no time allocated for it in the teaching schedule. Furthermore, neither research publications nor research activities are recognized or rewarded in any way.

In Italy, the career paths of HMEIs and university faculty are rigidly separated, with no possibility of interchange between the two systems. The current situation is paradoxical: although HMEIs confer degrees equivalent to those awarded by universities—at the bachelor’s, master’s, and doctoral levels—the legal status of professors in HMEIs remains entirely distinct from that of university staff. This discrepancy results in significant disadvantages in terms of salary, workload, and career advancement for those working in HMEIs. The situation is especially detrimental to the field of musicology, as it creates an institutional divide that hampers meaningful interaction and scholarly exchange. Moreover, staff in HMEIs currently are unable to access individual research funding. This presents yet another paradox: doctoral students are allocated personal research funds, while their supervising professors are not.

⁶ https://www.snesup.pt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Vencimentos_e_quotas_irs_2025.pdf [accessed: 29.05.2025].

In Albania, the academic career path for musicologists follows several stages. Initially, after completing masters and doctoral studies, musicologists begin as lectures in their faculty. Following 5 years of work experience to be promoted to Associate Professor, a musicologist requires the following: publishing scholarly works, monographs, textbooks and articles in journals ranked in Scopus/Web of Science Indexed journals; participation in International conferences, supervision of students research, and the supervision of master's theses. The only Albanian HMEI is the Faculty of Music. Musicology is a program speciality within the Department of Composition, Musicology, Conducting, and Music Pedagogy within the Faculty of Music. Particularly in the field of historical musicology subjects such as music history, aesthetics, and research models are assigned within the Faculty. In other contexts, musicology is embedded within the disciplines of conducting, and music pedagogy. Following the Bologna reforms, universities use ranks Assistant, Associate, Professor. The presence of musicologists has often been a consequence of early hiring processes in which candidates holding PhDs, frequently in musicology, have been appointed.

The academic career path for musicologists in Ukrainian HMEIs (music academies) typically follows a structured progression through several key stages: 1) Entry Level: After completing a Master's degree, musicologists usually begin as assistants or lecturers, focusing primarily on teaching while developing their research profile; 2) Mid-Career: Advancement to Associate Professor (Docent) requires obtaining a Candidate of Sciences (PhD) degree, publishing scholarly works in Ukrainian and international journals, and developing a teaching portfolio. For musicologists specifically, artistic achievements like concert performances, recordings, and competition awards are highly valued alongside traditional research outputs; 3) Senior Level: Progression to Full Professor requires a Doctor of Sciences degree (higher doctoral qualification), substantial publication record, and significant contribution to the field. This typically includes monographs, textbooks, and articles in prestigious journals. Research expectations for musicologists in Ukrainian music academies are multifaceted: academic publications are required, with increasing emphasis on international visibility through publications in Scopus/Web of Science indexed journals; participation in scholarly conferences (domestic and international); integration of performance practice with theoretical research; supervision of student research at various levels; development of innovative teaching methodologies and materials; active participation in the broader musical community through critiques, reviews, and public engagement. The unique aspect for musicologists is the dual valuation of both traditional scholarly research and artistic achievements, with the latter being formally recognized in the qualification and promotion process through concert activities, recordings, and competition achievements.

2.6. Institutional mobility

A key consideration is the extent to which professors employed in HMEIs are able to move between their institution and universities as part of a standard career trajectory.

In the Netherlands, contact and work possibilities between HMEIs and university institutions is fluid. It is possible to hold a position at both simultaneously, and guest lecturers can move between both sorts of institutions. Within an HMEI, university professors can be “hired in” for a limited number of hours as special advisors for the masters students.

In Spain, HMEIs professors are generally not allowed to hold additional jobs, due to incompatibility laws. However, there are certain exceptions. Professors may be permitted to teach part time at a university as an Associate Lecturer (*Profesor Asociado*), or to work in the public cultural sector. That said, approval for such secondary employment is not automatic. Teaching schedules must not overlap, and regional governments can still deny the request if other legal conditions are not met. In any case, being a professor in an HMEI does not automatically grant access to university teaching. Universities have their own independent selection processes, and any professor in an HMEI who wishes to teach at a university must start from scratch and meet all the specific requirements set by the university system.

According to the Lithuanian Law on Science and Studies, the academic title of professor holds equal formal status across higher education institutions, including both universities and academies. However, in practice, direct transfer of this status between institutions can be challenging due to differing institutional requirements and expectations. While general national guidelines for academic ranks exist, each higher education institution sets its own specific criteria, which can result in limited mobility between universities and academies where there are differences in expectation. At Lithuanian Academy of Music and Theatre, professors undergo a certification process every five years, during which they must demonstrate continued professional and academic activity in line with the institution’s expectations. Should these criteria not be fully met, the title may be revised, for example, by transitioning to the rank of associate professor. Additionally, remuneration for professorial positions may vary between universities and academies, reflecting institutional policies and funding structures.

The Turkish Law of Higher Education no. 2547 regulates inter-institutional assignments under the articles 37 (“university support on applied fields”), 38 (“appointment in other state institutions and foundations”), 39 (“appointment in domestic and international academic institutions”), 40 (“inter-institutional solidarity”), and 41 (“meeting the faculty need”). Through various bureaucratic processes in universities, HMEIs professors can be appointed to different positions in different institutions for short or long term, these institutions can be other universities, art foundations, Ministry of Culture and Tourism, state ensembles, music high schools etc.

The flexibility usually depends on personal relations and the law does not guarantee job security.

HMEIs and universities in Greece do not share an institutional framework in terms of teaching structure or academic mobility. Nevertheless, institutions such as the Athens Conservatoire—despite the constitutional restriction that limits the provision of higher education to public-sector institutions—meet the structural and academic standards of a higher education establishment. It maintains collaborations with university bodies, and a number of its faculty members are actively engaged in teaching and research through their university affiliations.

In the UK, academic rank and progression, whether at universities or HMEIs, is not governed by statute but is defined at institutional level. In practical terms, career paths between universities and HMEIs are permeable. A professor of musicology in these institutions would be considered of equal status as a university professor of musicology, and academics move freely between both in either direction. Musicology lecturers below professorial level, given that they are often part-time and non-permanent, can and do hold teaching roles simultaneously at a university and a HMEIs, thus creating a pragmatic link between institutions.

Although public higher education institutions in Portugal are autonomous and mobility between them is theoretically possible through mechanisms such as secondment, in practice transitions always occur through new recruitment processes rather than formal transfer.

Case study: Institutional Mobility in Ukrainian Musicology

Institutional mobility in Ukraine's academic landscape for musicologists presents both challenges and opportunities. The case of Professor Yuriy Yasinovskiy provides an illuminating example of successful mobility between different types of institutions. Yuriy Yasinovskiy began his distinguished career by establishing and heading a department at the Lviv National Music Academy (previously known as Lviv State Conservatory), where he specialised in Byzantine and Ukrainian sacred music. His expertise in medieval musical manuscripts and early Ukrainian musical culture positioned him as a leading figure in Ukrainian musicology. In a notable career transition, Yasinovskiy later moved to the Ukrainian Catholic University (UCU) in Lviv, where he founded and led another academic department. This institutional shift represented not merely a change in workplace but a strategic expansion of his academic influence and research scope. What makes this case particularly significant is that UCU became home to the Professor Peter Wolff Library collection due to Yasinovskiy's presence. This valuable collection of musicological materials enhanced the university's research infrastructure and created a new centre for musicological studies outside the traditional conservatory system. This case demonstrates that institutional mobility in Ukraine can: allow scholars to broaden their academic influence across different types of institutions; enable the transfer of specialised knowledge between traditional music academies and universities; facilitate the development of new research centers and collections; create opportunities for cross-disciplinary collaboration. For Ukrainian musicologists, such mobility patterns represent an important

strategy for career development beyond the confines of a single institution, particularly valuable in a field where opportunities within any single institution may be limited.

3. Curriculum design and pedagogical approaches

Given the role of HMEIs as institutions for the training of practical musicians, the question may reasonably be asked as to how essential historical musicology (in teaching or research) is to their primary mission. There is a broad consensus, whether for pragmatic or ideological reasons, that it is fundamental. It is not possible to imagine a performer with absolutely no need for music-historical knowledge or awareness. But in practical terms, the level of engagement with historical musicology differs greatly. Almost universally, the teaching of music history is a required part of HMEI curricula, and is often (but not necessarily) taught by staff employed as musicologists. But much of this teaching can be in the nature of survey courses which are not research led, even if often taught by trained musicologists with PhDs.

There are different models for how music history is included in curricula. It can be taught as a separate course; here the standard model is the historical survey style, from early historical periods through to the current developments in which students get broad knowledge about the context and factual knowledge, sometimes known as “Introduction to history of music”. It is also delivered in combination with other topics, such as music theory, historical performance, research-led projects, or research methodology (including bibliographies, etc.)-oriented courses.

There are higher music educational institutions with established (historical) musicology study programmes. Study programs include historical musicology disciplines and systematic musicology, with national music history as an important part of the curriculum. Such curricula include theoretical and practical disciplines, alongside music-history/musicology, harmony, form, counterpoint, orchestration, ear training, instrument playing, choir, and other broader subjects such as aesthetics, art history, sociology, research methodology, world music, and music in media. There is also usually a strong emphasis on individual research projects. The pedagogical approach often combines lectures and seminars, group discussions and analysis of musical pieces in the historical context. Upon completing BA studies, students may pursue MA and work on their scholarly-oriented dissertation.

Case study: Musicological training in Belgrade

The musicology module at the Faculty of Music, University of Arts in Belgrade, offers students a comprehensive music education with wide possibilities for the choice of the profession. Students develop

professional competencies in various scientific fields. Through an interdisciplinary approach characteristic of musicology, they are empowered for creative, individual research work or participation in research projects. By applying and integrating acquired contemporary knowledge of scientific research and theory, students develop skills for answering complex contextual musicological issues by applying scientific methods.⁷

Case study: Historical Musicology Pedagogy in Ukraine

Curriculum design and pedagogical approaches in historical musicology in Ukraine are governed by state educational standards in the field of musical art. These standards include the Higher Education Standard for the first (bachelor's) level in speciality 025 "Musical Art" approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (Order No. 727 dated May 24, 2019) and the Higher Education Standard for the second (master's) level in speciality 025 "Musical Art" (Order No. 368 dated October 4, 2018), both of which include "Musicology" as a specialization. While these standards establish general competencies and learning outcomes, the specific content of each course depends largely on the instructor's pedagogical vision and academic freedom in determining the subject matter, methodological approaches, and assessment strategies. This flexibility allows for diverse approaches to teaching historical musicology that can respond to contemporary trends in the field whilst preserving Ukrainian musical heritage and traditions.

3.1. HMEI vs university curricula

The curriculum for historical musicology often differs significantly between HMEIs and universities across Europe, although there are important areas of overlap. The key differences lie in focus, depth, and purpose of training. HMEIs generally prioritize performance and applied music skills, with musicology serving as an integrated subject that provides performers with context for the repertoire they play. This performance-oriented approach stands in contrast to universities, which typically treat musicology as a distinct academic discipline with emphasis on critical theory, historiography, research methods, and scholarly writing. These differences are evident in assessment methods as well. HMEIs tend to evaluate students through written exams, oral presentations, and performance-linked essays that connect historical knowledge to interpretive decisions. Universities more commonly assess students through research papers, theoretical analysis, and often require these featuring original research.

The tension between practical and research-oriented training manifests differently across European countries. In France, for example, the Conservatoire National Supérieur de Musique et de Danse de Paris (CNSMDP) offers a degree primarily aimed at musicians, focusing on repertoire knowledge, historical style, and performance practice. By contrast, the Sorbonne Université takes a more research-oriented approach, emphasizing historical sources, palaeography, ethnomusicology, and analytical methods.

⁷ <https://www.fmu.bg.ac.rs/studies/science-of-music/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

Case study: Dual Pathways in Polish Historical Musicology. Universities vs. Music Academies

The Polish higher education system offers two different paths for widely understood historical musicology studies. The first path is the university route, based on the German/Austrian model of ‘Musikwissenschaft’ and referred to as musicology. The second, developed by a wide network of music academies, is referred to as music theory. The areas of both subdisciplines are partly overlapping, but specific, distinct aspects of each of them can be identified. For these two paths, the curricula are different.

Musicology in universities offers a full range of subjects from the fields of systematic musicology, ethnomusicology, and music history. Students have more teaching hours for each musical period (including lectures, laboratories, seminars, etc.), usually run by specialists in a particular field. On the other hand, they have very little contact with music practice; they do not have to play any instrument; however, they have some choir/singing classes.

In contrast, in music academies students of music theory are much more involved in practical skills like ear training, harmony, playing instruments, etc. Typically, they are already trained musicians with a music high-school diploma, not required in the case of musicology. Music theory students usually have much closer contact with contemporary music, as composition is taught at the same faculty, and they attend the same classes together with young composers. Teaching the history of music in music academies is often done by people who are not specialists in a given historical period, typically involving fewer teaching hours. This is particularly the case with regard to early music. As a result, the research done by music theorists is much more often focused on modern music (e.g. documenting the output of their colleague composers and masters, like Krzysztof Penderecki in the case of Kraków). Exceptions include researchers employed in music academies, who deal with music composed before 1900. These are both trained musicologists (later employed at music academies) and music theorists.

Occasionally, important and valuable research is also conducted in music academies by performers specializing in early music. This includes not only performance-based research but also purely musicological studies, publications, and editions meeting the highest scientific standards.

Case study: Musicology in Croatia. Institutional Limits and Cross-Disciplinary Challenges

Comparison to The Netherlands

Croatia is a relatively small country, with only one Department of Musicology in Zagreb, housed at the University of Zagreb Academy of Music. The University of Zagreb awards an integrated (BA+MA) 5-year programme in musicology: MA theses can be supervised only by teaching staff with a PhD in musicology. In common with the Netherlands, graduates in this integrated five-year MA degree programme, from the field of performing arts, combined with a final recital, have to write a short MA thesis with a musicological approach. Their supervisors can be any member of the performing teaching staff, including musicians, who are not always competent to supervise an academic paper. This situation is comparable to Poland. In the Netherlands the final work is always evaluated by a faculty member with a PhD. Currently a PhD in musicology is awarded only in Zagreb in cooperation with the Faculty of the Humanities and Social Sciences and there is no doctorate in artistic research in music. There are plans to introduce artistic research in Croatia as well, which could lead to the same problems encountered in the Netherlands: the ability to choose between a PhD in musicology and a doctorate in artistic research to advance one’s career and get a significant salary raise; the option not to have a proper musicological

supervisor could lead to the problem of candidates opting for the (perceived) less demanding option, in which case the musicological aspects of these degrees would suffer as a result.

The institutional frameworks where musicologists acquire their PhDs vary. It can happen as part of a doctoral programme in musicology (at the University of Zagreb or abroad - which is also common), but it can also happen under the auspices of a doctoral programme in some other branch of the field of humanities (for example - philology or cultural studies), but with a musicological topic, under the supervision of a professor of musicology not (necessarily) employed at the same faculty.

PhD candidates do not have to have an MA in musicology in order to be able to enrol in a PhD in musicology (in Zagreb) or in a musicological topic. Therefore, there is a certain degree of equivalence at the entry level for these programmes: people with a similar degree - music or another branch of the humanities - can enrol as well. This has both advantages and disadvantages: on the one hand, a very small field such as musicology benefits from being open to colleagues from other similar fields (such as music as a performing art or music theory). On the other hand, the transition from one discipline to another is demanding and sometimes the quality of the research suffers as a result.

3.2. Degree programs across Europe

The implementation of the Bologna system has significantly shaped musicology education across European HMEIs, though national variations remain substantial. The Bologna framework necessitated the definition of modules with deliberately open names to allow flexibility in seminar content. For example, at the Rostock University of Music and Drama in Germany, historical musicology modules are designated simply as "Music History I and II" and "Music History of your choice," with seminar content varying each semester.

Not all European HMEIs offer dedicated degree programs in historical musicology. In **Poland**, almost all conservatories offer BA/MA programs in music theory (not to be confused with musicology), while in other countries, the academic degrees vary considerably. In the **UK**, musicology provision is integrated into three- or four-year BA/BMus programs at undergraduate level. At postgraduate level only one institution (the Royal Birmingham Conservatoire) offers a dedicated MA in Musicology. **Croatia** provides integrated BA/MA programs (five-year curricula that combine bachelor's and master's level work). In **Serbia**, two higher education music institutions (Belgrade and Novi Sad) offer BA (4 years), MA (1 year) and PhD program (3 years).

In **France**, the vast majority of conservatories are pre-college, meaning that only the HMEIs can provide professional level diplomas linked to musicology (in collaboration with musicology departments at universities); nevertheless, it has to be stressed that only the two CNSMD can offer full historical musicology degrees aligned to those of the universities' music departments.

In **Albania**, only the Faculty of Music offers degree programmes and doctoral degrees in Musicology.. The faculty has been proactive in developing postgraduate training; it initiated the Postgraduate School of Musicology in 2005, followed by a Level II Master's programme in 2009, and recently launched Cycle III doctoral studies in 2023.

The availability of doctoral programs also varies significantly. In **Austria**, four public universities (Vienna, Graz, Innsbruck, and Salzburg) award doctoral degrees in musicology, as do three arts universities (University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna, Mozarteum University Salzburg, and University of the Arts Graz). In the UK, seven of nine conservatories offer PhDs in Music - some independently, some accredited by universities - which may combine aspects of artistic or compositional practice with a written thesis. In **The Netherlands**, only two universities (Amsterdam and Utrecht) offer musicology degrees, while conservatories are unable to offer a PhD unless in conjunction with a university.

Case study: Higher Musicological Education in Ukraine. Institutional Structures and Specializations from Bachelor's to Doctoral Levels

In Ukraine, bachelor's programs in musicology typically span 4 years and provide a comprehensive foundational education in music theory, history, and analysis. These programs share similar structures across institutions. At the National Music Academy of Ukraine (Kyiv), bachelor's students can pursue a Musicology specialization under Musical Arts (025), or alternatively Cultural Studies with a music focus (034). The curriculum covers traditional European music theory alongside Ukrainian musical heritage. The Lviv National Music Academy offers a 4-year Bachelor of Music in Musicology with specialization options in General Musicology or Ethnomusicology. Its program includes the focused study of medieval music within the Department of Music Medievalistics. Odessa National Music Academy provides Bachelor's programs in the speciality "025 Musical Arts" with a concentration on under its Piano-Theoretical and Vocal Faculty, incorporating foundational training in music theory, history, and analysis. Kharkiv National University of Arts offers a 4-year Bachelor's degree in Music Art (025) with an educational program in Musicology and Composition. The curriculum includes core theoretical subjects like harmony and polyphony alongside Ukrainian and international music history. Master's programs in musicology (typically 1.5-2 years) offer more specialised research training with distinct methodological approaches at each institution. Kyiv's Master's in Musicology (Musical Arts 025) and Music Cultural Studies (034) both require for qualifications paper defence, and language proficiency, emphasizing advanced research methodologies and specialised knowledge in selected areas. Lviv offers a 1.75-year Master of Music in Musicology with specializations in Historical Musicology, Ethnomusicology, or Music Theory. Its program is distinguished by options to focus specifically on medieval music studies through the Department of Music Medievalistics.

Doctoral studies (PhD/Doctor of Philosophy) in musicology represent the highest level of academic specialization, typically lasting 4 years. The National Music Academy in Kyiv offers PhD programs in Musical Arts (025) and Cultural Studies (034), alongside Doctor of Arts programs for those who already hold PhDs. * The academy also provides Creative Postgraduate Studies focused on performance specializations. Lviv offers PhD in Musicology with research-based structure supplemented by coursework. Its doctoral program maintains particular strength in medieval music research and ethnomusicology, connected to the Laboratory of Music Ethnology. Odessa maintains doctoral studies in "025 Musical Arts" (musicology) and a specialised academic council for dissertation defence in "Musical Art" (17.00.03), enabling advanced research in specialised areas. Kharkiv offers a PhD Program in speciality 17.00.03 - "Music Art" (established 1993) and a newer Doctor of Arts Program (established 2022) focusing on creative-performative doctoral work.

Case study: Music Education in Greece. Dual Pathways through Conservatories and University Departments

Greek music education consists of Conservatories (private, except the State Conservatory in Thessaloniki) and University Departments (public, except some few recent ones which are not discussed here). As a general principle, Conservatories in Greece focus primarily on the instruction of music performance encompassing all Schools of the vocal and instrumental curriculum of the Western Symphonic Orchestra as defined in the 19th c. including their individual subcategories, whereas University Departments specialize in Musicology—encompassing Historical and Systematic Musicology, Ethnomusicology, Byzantine Musicology, Music Pedagogy, Music Acoustics, and Digitized Musicology. The most prominent (major) conservatories in historical order, include the Athens Conservatoire, the State Conservatory of Thessaloniki, the Hellenic Conservatory and the National Conservatory. The certification of a graduate with the title of Diploma signifies official recognition that the individual possesses the highest level of knowledge in the discipline from which they graduate and that the Conservatory has to offer. The *Ptychion* (from the Greek word “Πτυχίον”, meaning “half of a folded paper”) represents a lower academic qualification than the *Diploma* (“Δίπλωμα” literally, “fully folded paper”), and limits the holder in both performance and teaching capacities (e.g., eligible to teach only up to the “Advanced Class” level). Historically, the need to formally certify music education through the Diploma can be traced back to the Reformation Period of the Athens Conservatoire in 1894.

Conservatories in Greece award the above state-degrees which are formally recognized by the Ministry of Culture, but have not yet been formally aligned with the levels of the National Qualifications Framework which corresponds to the European one. The *Ptychion*, should correspond to level 6 of the European Qualifications Framework, as well as the *Diploma*, should correspond to level 7 of the EQF.

This formal issue, of course, does not in any way diminish the immense contribution of the Conservatories—and especially the prestigious Athens Conservatoire—to Greek musical life..

3.3. Module design and content integration

The integration of historical musicology into conservatory curricula displays considerable national and institutional variation, though certain common patterns emerge. In many conservatories, historical musicology is embedded within broader music education and seen as enriching or contextualising the artistic practice that is at the core of the curriculum, rather than existing as a stand-alone discipline.

In Greece, for example, conservatories typically organize music history education along three parallel tracks within the same curriculum:

"History of Music" focusing on significant historical events, people, cultures, and works (global and European), taught over two years

"Morphology" concentrating on European musical forms as defined primarily after the Renaissance, taught for one year

"Organology" examining the history of musical instruments, taught for one year

This approach allows for a broad ranging but practice-oriented engagement with historical materials.

In German-speaking countries, music theory is traditionally regarded as a practical/artistic subject, while in Poland, for example, it is partly historically oriented (although focused almost exclusively on contemporary music). This distinction affects how historical content is integrated into the curriculum and taught to students.

In the Lithuanian Academy of Musik and Theatre, where musicology has a longstanding tradition, the term "musicology" is no longer used in the official titles of study programmes. The former BA in Musicology has been restructured and is now offered as a BA in Music Studies/Musical Research, while the MA programme is titled MA in Research and Communication, within which musicology can be pursued as a specialisation. Despite these changes in programme names, the academy's music faculty continues to host a dedicated Department of Musicology.

The implementation of the Bologna standards has generally led to greater uniformity in the formal structure of musicology education across Europe, with 180-ECTS Bachelor's and 120-ECTS Master's becoming the norm. However, the actual content and pedagogical approaches often continue to reflect distinct national traditions and institutional priorities.

4. Research capabilities in historical musicology

A critical question in HMEIs, with their principal focus towards performance and the training of practical musicians, is the extent to which historical musicology, whether at the level of teaching or research, is integrated within their core aims rather than being simply an add-on. Here the boundaries are often blurry, given that historically oriented research can be conducted into performance itself. Furthermore, the boundaries between historical musicology, music theory, and performance are not always clearly defined. Given this, the range of fruitful potential synergies may be wider than initially suspected. As such, examination of this in terms of models is a helpful starting point.

4.1. Models of research integration

A comprehensive summary of all of the ways in which research and the practices of HMEIs can be integrated - including both those that are abstractly conceivable as well as those that are currently or have been previously implemented in specific HMEIs - would exceed the space available here. However, several main distinctive models can be identified, often coexisting within national systems.

Some HMEIs maintain autonomous research departments dedicated to historical musicology. These institutions integrate research into their educational frameworks, maintain dedicated research staff, pursue independent research agendas, and often publish their own series. The Schola Cantorum Basiliensis in Switzerland exemplifies

this approach, housing a dedicated research department specializing in historical music practice from the Middle Ages to the 19th century. Similarly, the University Mozarteum Salzburg in Austria has established the Institute for the History of Musical Reception and Interpretation, focusing on reception and interpretation history.

In other contexts, research in historical musicology occurs primarily within the framework of Historically Informed Performance (HIP) projects. Rather than existing as an autonomous academic discipline, historical inquiry is integrated into artistic practice, especially within departments or programs dedicated to early music. This approach is particularly prevalent in HMEIs with strong early music traditions, such as the Royal Conservatoire of The Hague, the Conservatoire National Supérieur de Musique et de Danse de Lyon, and the Escola Superior de Música de Catalunya.

A third model involves HMEIs participating in musicological research through collaboration with external academic institutions. This cooperation occurs both at the personal level, through individual teachers affiliated with university research centers, and at the institutional level, through partnerships with universities or research bodies. For example, the Lost&Found project⁸, coordinated by CESEM at NOVA University Lisbon, explores neglected repertoires of mid to late sixteenth-century Portuguese polyphony, with participation from conservatory-based performers and teachers.

In Germany, the Academies' Program of the Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities (Akademienprogramm der Union der deutschen Akademien der Wissenschaften)⁹ is a strong supporter of research projects, especially in historical musicological editions. The number of staff involved in the third-party funded projects also has a direct impact on the curriculum, as they contribute their specialist expertise and topics to the modules of historical musicology.

In yet another model, some HMEIs engage in historical musicological research not through dedicated research departments or structured collaborations, but through the institutional value of their collections and the initiatives of individual staff members. In these cases, research activity often emerges from the presence of significant archives, libraries, or instrument collections, and is often driven by conservatory-based scholars and performers whose work connects pedagogy, performance, and historical inquiry. Several Italian conservatories—such as San Pietro a Majella in Naples, Giuseppe Verdi in Milan, and Benedetto Marcello in Venice—as well as the Athens Conservatoire, house collections dating back to the 17th-19th centuries that serve as the foundation for research projects involving cataloguing, digitalisation, critical editions, and historiographical study. While external scholars may carry out much of the research, it is frequently enabled and supported by in-house librarians, teachers, and musicians, with results feeding back into performance and teaching within the HMEIs itself.

⁸ <https://www.lostandfound.fcsh.uni.pt>

⁹ [Akademienprogramm](#)

4.2. Research support and funding

Funding for historical musicology research in HMEIs comes from various sources, including internal institutional funding and external grants. Internal funding typically covers research activities when HMEIs maintain dedicated research departments, as exemplified by the Athens Conservatoire, which can support researcher salaries but requires external funding for publications.

External funding sources include national agencies, mixed funding (combining European and national sources), European Union programs, and private patronage. National funding bodies, such as Portugal's Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, Switzerland's Haute École Spécialisée de la Suisse Occidentale, and the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation, support research projects at HMEIs. Mixed funding models include Greece's ESPA program, which combines European Commission funding with support from the Greek state.

European Union programs like Horizon Europe, Creative Europe, and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions represent potential funding sources, although HMEIs secure such grants less frequently than universities. This discrepancy most likely stems from universities' greater experience and institutional capacity in applying for competitive European funding. Universities typically maintain dedicated research offices and project management teams and face considerable pressure to secure external funding as part of their financial and strategic planning. HMEIs tend to be smaller institutions and, as a consequence, have fewer administrative resources in house to apply for and administer such grants.

Despite these challenges, some HMEIs have successfully secured funding for research projects. For instance, Italy has leveraged the EU's Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) to support research projects led by HMEIs, including work on persecuted composers, critical editions of neglected Italian piano repertoire, and investigations into cultural and artistic heritage.

4.3. Motivations for research

Motivations for conducting historical musicology research in HMEIs operate at both institutional and personal levels. Institutionally, HMEIs pursue research to attract additional funding, improve their rankings and status, demonstrate academic leadership, and position themselves as equal to universities within higher education systems.

Research activities also enhance the international profiles of HMEIs through collaborations with similar institutions abroad. Some HMEIs view science (musicology) and artistic research as complementary or even equivalent, blurring the distinction

between these fields and encouraging interdisciplinary work. More broadly, research contributes to national policies on arts education, culture, and science. National and international strategies for progress and innovation are primarily associated with research, which also pertain to HMEIs.

At the personal level, teachers and researchers in HMEIs are motivated by intellectual curiosity, a desire to deeply understand musical phenomena, and a commitment to expanding knowledge in the field. Research represents a space where persistence and critical thinking converge, offering opportunities for both intellectual and personal growth. For many, research is considered not just a career path, but a lifelong commitment to learning and making meaningful contributions to the field.

Research activities contribute, in addition, to professional development and career advancement, particularly as HMEIs increasingly align with university models. Many HMEI teachers with long-standing careers as performers or educators have traditionally engaged in informal or practice-based inquiry driven by artistic exploration or pedagogical refinement. Depending on the permeability of roles and qualifications, some of these staff have made a successful transition within their institution from practitioner to (primarily or entirely) historical musicologist.

As HMEIs shift towards academic institutional structures akin to universities, professionals face growing pressure to formalize and document their investigative practices to meet new expectations regarding career progression, evaluation, and institutional visibility. As for applications by candidates for these newly formalized positions, it has to be noted that those are highly competitive. HMEIs usually look for diversely qualified profiles, possessing a PhD in musicology, usually in addition to degrees and prizes often obtained within HMEIs as instrumentalists or composers. In summary, the “polymath” figure is still at the heart of the employment process of most of these establishments.

Case study: Ukrainian Musicologists and the Politics of Memory

The motivations driving young Ukrainian musicologists extend beyond traditional academic pursuits. Contemporary researchers are deeply motivated by enhancing historically informed performance practices while simultaneously recovering works by composers who were censored or repressed during previous political regimes. The formation of national cultural identity serves as a central motivating force, with scholars viewing their research as an essential process of decolonization and reclamation of Ukraine's musical heritage. Young musicologists are particularly dedicated to establishing Ukraine's distinct musical traditions within the broader European cultural context, seeing their scholarly work as both intellectual pursuit and cultural resistance against historical erasure and appropriation.

4.4. Research output and impact assessment

As HMEIs become more and more embedded in the research infrastructures of their respective national and transnational systems of governance and funding, their research performance (in terms of outputs and impact) is measured along the same lines as that of universities. In the UK, which has the longest-standing and mature system of research assessment in the European Higher Education sector, HMEIs have become increasingly active in—and their internal support and staffing structures driven by—subsequent iterations of the Research Excellence Framework (REF),¹⁰ which distributes substantial block-grant funding to institutions based on a seven- to eight-year comprehensive evaluation cycle. HMEIs have been aided in this by a definition of research that treats artistic and practice-based approaches as equivalent to historical, theoretical or empirical research, and by an increasing emphasis on “impact”, defined in the UK context as benefitting non-higher education contexts, society and the economy. The consideration of impact is slowly starting to be considered further as an important assessment in other European countries, mostly when applying for important European funding.¹¹

Some HMEIs in German-speaking countries have their own publication series (e.g., qualification theses (Dr. and Habilitation), monographs, conference proceedings, etc.), connecting the institutional profile to an established publication location.

Case study: Evaluating Music Research in Serbia and Türkiye. Shifting Policies and Artistic Impact

In Serbia, higher music education institutions offering PhD’s in musicology, ethnomusicology, etc. are accredited as scientific-research institutions by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation. Research performance is assessed by the Ministry, based on the same criteria as for other humanities. Due to frequent shifts in the governmental oversight of science—whether as an independent ministry or under the Ministry of Education or Innovation—there are many changes in the assessment systems, the last one being eScience¹² (still under construction).

In Türkiye, fields of fine arts are evaluated differently than other academic fields, counting artistic performance towards impact. A historical musicologist can be tenured both with their publications and their concerts and album releases. “Societal impact” is an emerging category in quality assessment of academic work and most performances are evaluated within this category. Combining academic research with artistic research is also supported by the Turkish National Foundation of Science and Technology (TUBITAK¹³), enabling performances related to research findings.

¹⁰ <https://2029.ref.ac.uk/>

¹¹ For further thoughts about the consideration of impact in historical musicology, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118211>

¹² [eScience](#)

¹³ [CORNET \(Kollektif Araştırma Ağı\) | TÜBİTAK | Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Araştırma Kurumu](#)

5. Perspectives on future opportunities

The current diversity of historical musicology within HMEIs presents both challenges and opportunities for the future, as this report demonstrates. This section of the report addresses: the need for a sustained cartographic effort concerning the place of music history in HMEIs (5.1.); the relationship between HMEIs and universities (5.2.); stakeholder perspectives (5.3.); access to research funds (5.4.); issues of diversity and inclusivity (5.5.); future frameworks (5.6.); and the challenges posed by artificial intelligence (5.7.).

5.1. The Need for a Lasting Cartographic Effort

What this report highlights—while also attempting to address—is the fragmentation of information concerning the place of music history within HMEIs. This undertaking is unprecedented, underscoring the originality and necessity of the present report. As in the case of music history in universities (see the 2025 report¹⁴), there is no centralised or easily comparable information regarding training programmes, degrees and their equivalencies, career paths, course content, and more. Beyond this lack of centralisation, however, there is considerable variation—not only between countries, but often within them—where diverse types of institutions operate under widely differing practices, even where there are commonalities in statute.

A common reference framework does exist, most notably through the AEC, which promotes higher music education across Europe and fosters cooperation between institutions. The AEC also provides guidelines intended to ensure quality and encourage innovation in music education. Yet, as this report makes clear, the current landscape remains highly diverse in terms of institutional, pedagogical, and administrative practices.¹⁵ What is urgently needed is a sustained, long-term effort to map existing teaching practices, job roles, career pathways, curricula, and relationships with universities, among other dimensions. This effort must not be a one-time initiative, but a durable and structured commitment. Only through the consolidation of such data and the networking of individuals and institutions can historical musicology within HMEIs achieve a real institutional presence. In other words, this field must be given substance. The process towards this aim must begin with a long-term, cartographic undertaking.

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14621706>

¹⁵ <https://aec-music.eu/media/2024/05/Policy-Paper-on-key-criteria-for-innovative-music-teacher-education-.pdf>, <https://aec-music.eu/media/2021/05/AEC-Framework-Document-Quality-Assurance-and-Accreditation-in-Higher-Music-Education-EN.pdf>.

5.2. Evolving relationships between HMEIs and universities

The relationship between HMEIs and universities in Europe continues to evolve, with significant implications for the future of historical musicology education and research. Several trends point toward increasing integration and cooperation between these institutional types, although distinctive traditions and missions persist.

The Bologna Process has been a major driver of convergence, encouraging HMEIs to adopt structures and standards compatible with university education. For example, in Italy, the full implementation of this process has laid the groundwork for deeper integration between HMEIs and the broader European academic landscape, aligning the degrees with university qualifications, using the same three-cycle structure and the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS). This process has not been completed in all countries. In Greece, for example, the HMEI degrees have not yet been aligned with the European-equivalent levels of the National Qualifications Framework.

In other cases, despite the implementation of the Bologna process, the difficulty in establishing equivalences between HMEI and university qualifications continues. In France, there is a structural division between music academy and university diplomas, creating difficulties for the professional development of young musicologists. Joint degree programs offer a potential solution to this problem. Whilst the national conservatories of Paris and Lyon are at the forefront of this approach, offering a master's degree that validates both conservatory and university diplomas, the progressive decentralisation of higher arts education is slowly enabling the development of fruitful partnerships between HMEIs and university music departments across the country. Although these joint degree programs are more often than not aimed at instrumentalists, it would be possible to imagine similar collaborations on musicology courses, currently far too sparse to favour the employment of young musicologists. In other national contexts, joint diplomas are being increasingly created to solve institutional issues, offering young musicologists greater employability through diversity of experience.

Throughout Europe, these developments are fostering closer collaboration between HMEIs and universities, particularly around shared research infrastructure, joint doctoral programmes, and artistic research initiatives. In Greece, for instance, the Music Departments of the Ionian University and the Athens Conservatoire are collaborating in the classification and documentation of the Athens Conservatoire Historical Archives, in writing and editing the 3 volumes of *History of Music in Greece (1453-2000)*, and in editing the journal *Neos Mousikos Hellenomnemon* dedicated to Greek History of Art-Music, etc.

In terms of PhD opportunities across Europe it should be noted that you can pursue PhDs in only a select number of HMEIs. This currently has far-reaching implications for diversity and inclusion, as well as for good employment practice within national HMEI frameworks. Attention needs to be given to countries where there are established

historical musicology programmes, but no possibility of pursuing a PhD in historical musicology. In these significant number of cases, employment panels face the paradox of having securely established programmes for historical musicology, but are only therefore able to appoint staff from abroad who hold PhD's within this discipline. The distorting effect of this could, perversely, mean that certain national programmes of PhD study dominate the employment in other, emerging countries. This depends on their status, the state laws, and whether the staff hold the local qualifications to be a PhD supervisor.

In addition to these circumstances, most of the PhDs offered in HMEIs are largely oriented towards artistic research. Whilst an interesting approach to draw new research possibilities and positively impact the diversity of curricula standards, these diplomas might not be deemed to be useful for both HMEIs and university employment, due to their hybridity between the artistic practice of the applicant and their musicological expectations. In the Netherlands, for example, the University of Amsterdam and the Conservatory of Amsterdam offer a program for students of both institutes (AMMA) and a doctoral trajectory within the DocARTES scheme Leiden University and the Royal Conservatory in The Hague combine forces (ACPA) to offer a PhD in artistic research granted by the university.

In Portugal, recent legislative changes allow polytechnic institutes (High Education Institutions) to award doctoral degrees, provided they meet strict research-related criteria, within other artistic institutions. This shift has intensified the need for robust research activity within HMEIs, as only faculties with an active research profile can participate in doctoral programmes. In addition, university research centres are showing growing interest in partnering with HMEIs to diversify their outputs, demonstrate the applicability and impact of their research, and to improve their overall evaluation ratings.

International cooperation is increasing as HMEIs become more active in European networks and exchange programs. For example, the AEC has made available to its members various tools that promote institutional relations between its members, as well as platforms that facilitate mobility and the implementation of the Erasmus program. These types of tools, in addition to the Erasmus+ program, have been key to the mobility of both students and teachers, and have contributed to the development of research and curriculum improvement. As a further example, in Türkiye, in addition to Erasmus+ collaborations, joint postgraduate programs in historical musicology between the Hacettepe University State Conservatory in Ankara and the Goethe University in Frankfurt are also on the agenda.

Incentives for institutions by national and international actors should continue to foster the improvement of these institutional relationships, which have proven useful for the development of HMEIs and university departments.

In order to improve and enhance the work and professional development of musicologists in both institutions, academic requirements should be unified.

Evaluation for research and pedagogical qualifications of HMEIs academics would help to ensure equivalent levels, allowing more flexibility for academics from both types of institutions. Scholars who hold a degree in musicology—regardless of whether it was obtained from an HMEI or a university—should be able to move freely between HMEIs and universities as places of employment. Such institutional flexibility will help in a better flow of musicological research, helping both institutions and academics access all the benefits of the Bologna Process.

5.3. Stakeholders perspectives (students, faculty, policy-makers) and social impact

From a student perspective, historical musicology in HMEIs poses an interesting challenge. Certainly at BA and MA level, the principal motivation by students to attend a HMEIs music program is to achieve advanced-level proficiency in musical practice, potentially alongside music pedagogy. The study of (or research into) historical musicology, by comparison, is regularly seen by students as a welcome addition at best, as a nuisance at worst. This only changes at Masters level in some instances (where HMEIs offer specialist musicology programmes) and definitively at PhD level, where HMEIs have carved out a distinctive profile of musicological research that attracts students in its own right.

This potentially dismissive attitude towards musicology is shared by at least parts of the performance faculty, who can also see musicology as a distraction from the perceived “true purpose” of HMEIs. This means that musicology can face a struggle for relevance from within, in terms of support or resourcing as much as with regard to its place in the curriculum. No policy or narrative that defines the place of musicology (in staffing, teaching, research) can ignore this tension. Even in circumstances where a regulation may indicate equivalence, there may be tacit practices that lead to different experiences.

In turn, recognising this tension can provide policy-makers with frameworks and arguments necessary not only to strengthen the place of historical musicology within curricula, but also to secure the status of those that provide it.

The efforts by musicology staff and leaders within HMEIs to increase research performance in terms of profile, visibility, external funding success, outputs, and impact is at least in part driven by a desire to increase the status and impact of musicology in an institutional context where support for the discipline is not self-evident. On the teaching side, the place of musicology in the curriculum cannot be taken for granted, either philosophically or practically: individually and collectively, musicologists need to keep making the case that the high-level study and knowledge of music is essential to a comprehensive degree program of music at BA/MA level. According to the ACE, a “professionally focused arts education” is “a quest for excellence in three areas: artistic practice; learning and teaching; --research and

innovation”¹⁶. Musicology has a potentially important role to play in all three of these areas, but the precise way in which it contributes to fulfilling these objectives needs to be explicitly articulated from an HMEI perspective.

An important exception is found in early music programmes, which—due to their inherently philological nature—tend to incorporate substantial elements of historical musicology into their curricula and attract students with a strong interest in historically informed approaches. Circulation between early music and historical musicology programmes is relatively common, with students often moving between the two areas in search of complementary perspectives.

5.4. Access to research funds

Access to research funding for historical musicology staff in HMEIs reveals significant structural inequalities when compared to university-based researchers or staff at research centres. This disparity stems mainly from the historical positioning of HMEIs as institutions primarily focused on artistic and professional training rather than on the systematic production of academic knowledge.

In many national systems, HMEIs lack established institutional frameworks to support research activities. Unlike universities, they often lack dedicated research offices, internal funding schemes, or structured mechanisms for allocating protected research time. These limitations hinder the ability of HMEI staff to sustain long-term research agendas. This is particularly the case in fields such as historical musicology, which require consistent access to archival materials, participation in international academic networks, and interdisciplinary methodological approaches.

Furthermore, the employment categories of HMEI staff—frequently designated as “artistic staff” or “teaching-artistic personnel”—can restrict their eligibility for competitive research applications and invitations. This issue is exacerbated by the fact that, in several European countries, HMEIs are not fully recognised as higher education institutions on equal terms with universities in matters of research. As a result, HMEI faculty members are often excluded from direct participation in publicly funded national and European research programmes. This exclusion represents a structural barrier that leaves the scholarly potential of many highly qualified musicologists working in HMEIs significantly under-utilised. It also creates asymmetries within the European Higher Education and Research Areas, depriving the broader field of musicology of valuable contributions grounded in artistic practice, local heritage, and diverse institutional settings.

To address the structural inequalities currently affecting HMEIs, several strategic measures should be considered to enhance access to research funding for academic staff in historical musicology. These include the formal recognition of HMEIs as research-performing institutions within national frameworks, their integration into

¹⁶ <https://aec-music.eu/about-aec/aec-vision-and-mission/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

existing research support systems, increased participation in European funding programmes, and stronger cooperation with universities and research centres.

Although HMEI staff are formally eligible to apply to several EU programmes—such as *Erasmus+*, *Creative Europe*, and the *European Open Science Cloud*—their participation remains limited. One reason is the way institutions are classified at the national level, which often restricts access to competitive funding. Another is the lack of internal research support within HMEIs. To address this, institutions and national authorities must enhance the communication of funding opportunities, making eligibility criteria clear to enable HMEI staff to advocate for participation. Institutions and national authorities should also strengthen research services and offer technical guidance. These steps are essential for HMEI researchers to manage complex application procedures and join international academic networks.

European funding programmes already offer multiple opportunities for academic staff in HMEIs, although not specifically in the field of historical musicology. However, to fully capitalise on these opportunities, greater institutional integration and stronger alignment with research and development priorities are necessary.

Whilst - at least in theory- the Horizon Europe programme represents one of the main avenues for accessing competitive research funding at the European level, in practice, HMEIs face significant obstacles to participation. Cluster 2, “Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society,” includes several topics directly relevant to historical musicology, such as cultural heritage, circulation of knowledge, sound history, and digital archives. Although HMEIs are formally eligible to participate, **most are not officially recognised as research-performing institutions at the national level,** which severely limits their access. This structural exclusion is compounded by the absence of a research track record, the lack of an internal research culture, and limited institutional experience in designing and managing competitive research proposals.

Despite these challenges, some institutions have begun to adopt proactive strategies to reverse this trend. A notable example is **ESMAE (Escola Superior de Música e Artes do Espetáculo, Porto)**, which has recently taken part in several European projects. While modest in scale, these initiatives aim to build institutional know-how, gain visibility, and establish international collaborations. Additionally, **many HMEIs already have extensive experience in managing Erasmus+ international mobility programmes** for both students and staff. This existing framework and experience base could serve as a foundation for gradually transitioning into collaborative research activities. By leveraging existing administrative capacity, skills, and transnational partnerships, HMEIs can begin integrating into wider academic consortia.

The involvement of the AEC could also play a decisive role in coordinating such efforts. The association has a proven track record in developing and managing European cooperation projects, primarily in the area of curriculum innovation and teaching. This experience can now be expanded to support initiatives focused on

research development, thus facilitating the structural inclusion of HMEIs within the European Research Area.

Finally, platforms such as the *European Open Science Cloud* and initiatives like *AI4Culture* and *Europeana* offer new possibilities for collaboration around heritage data and digital research methodologies. These tools, together with COST Actions—such as *EarlyMuse*—provide a flexible framework for networking, research mobility, the exchange of best practices, and the development of wider consortia. Several institutions have already engaged in such initiatives. For instance, **ESMUC (Barcelona)** contributed to the COST Action FP1302 *WOOD MUSICK*.

For academic staff in HMEIs to fully leverage these opportunities, it is crucial to enhance their institutional capacity. This includes ensuring access to advisory services, technical support, and training in developing competitive research proposals. Without targeted investment in these areas, structural barriers to participation will persist, and the research potential of HMEIs—particularly in fields such as historical musicology—will remain underutilised within the broader European Research Area.

For HMEIs to access competitive research funding on equal terms within the European Research Area, progress must be made towards achieving effective institutional equality with universities and recognised research centres. This parity must extend beyond formal recognition and translate into genuine access to funding, recognition of academic output, and full participation in scientific networks. A key step is the official recognition of HMEIs as research-performing institutions within national regulatory frameworks. This requires revising contractual and academic categories, and acknowledging the specific methodological and epistemological approaches found in artistic research, particularly in fields such as historical musicology. At the same time, HMEIs must be equipped with proper research support infrastructure, including project management services, specialised staff, and internal systems for evaluation and monitoring.

In conclusion, if the target truly aims to harness the full research potential of HMEIs, a structural shift is required. This transformation must go beyond formal recognition and involve active support for their integration as institutions capable of conducting historical and artistic research. Priority measures include the official recognition of HMEIs within national research funding frameworks, the development of internal research support infrastructure, and alignment with the academic standards that govern universities and research centres. As always, this is ultimately a question of policy prioritisation and financial investment. Existing strengths—such as extensive experience with Erasmus+ mobility programmes, growing involvement in European projects, and well-established international networks—offer a solid and impactful foundation upon which to build.

Crucially, if HMEI academic staff are to be eligible for the same research fundings as their university counterparts, they must also be subject to the same academic standards and evaluation mechanisms. For this reason, a coordinated European

strategy is needed to support the gradual integration of HMEIs into research systems, strengthening their internal capacities and securing their institutional recognition within a diverse, innovative, and culturally enriched European research ecosystem.

In parallel, there are fewer opportunities in national funding agencies. In some countries, like Spain, academic staff from HMEIs cannot apply to the research funding available to their counterparts in universities. The agencies could also create ring-fenced budgets that reflect the unique methods and knowledge systems of these institutions. Joint research units, co-supervised PhD programmes, and shared project proposals with universities would help reduce institutional gaps. These measures would also support the research capacity of HMEIs. Encouraging this type of inclusion would contribute to a more balanced and diverse European research landscape, especially in fields where history, art, and education intersect.

What is now needed is a coordinated effort at both national and European levels to remove structural barriers, foster institutional capacity-building, and ensure fair access to research funding and opportunities. Advancing in this direction would benefit not only HMEI staff and students but also enrich the diversity, innovation, and cultural depth of the European area as a whole.

5.5. Mission Statements and Gender Equality in HMEIs

The mission statements of HMEIs reflect the values and priorities of the institutions, often addressing key societal concerns. Today, themes such as diversity, inclusiveness, and gender equality have become central to the identity and responsibilities of higher education, including music education. While some HMEIs clearly articulate these values on their official websites, others either do not provide such information publicly or limit its accessibility due to language barriers or lack of transparency.

This chapter presents a comparative overview of how selected HMEIs across Europe formulate and communicate their mission statements, with particular attention to the inclusion of gender equality and related issues. Our aim is to highlight both the shared goals and existing discrepancies in how these values are represented.

5.5.1 ORGANISATIONAL AIMS

This subsection presents examples of institutional mission statements, based on official information available on their respective websites. The aim is to examine how these missions articulate their core values and strategic priorities. Key questions include: Are the stated visions for the future sufficiently innovative? To what extent does tradition continue to shape institutional identity? Do the missions address contemporary concerns such as sustainability, innovation, progressiveness, creativity,

and equal opportunities? The following examples offer insight into these dimensions¹⁷.

The University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna (mdw Vienna) commits to “democratic values, equal treatment, and diversity. Open communication, transparency, and participation are important for the University’s further development.” Besides, the mdw actively stands for gender equality and inclusion, trying “to create a discrimination-free study and work environment through the implementation of concrete measures to promote more equal participation by all members of the mdw community.”¹⁸

The Lithuanian Academy of Music and Theatre describes its mission as follows: to ensure sustainable development of art and artistic research, to participate in shaping the country's artistic education and cultural policy, to foster the spiritual harmony of society and national identity, to educate the most talented youth in art - creative, proactive, entrepreneurial, open to Lithuania and the world. Vision: "Akademija'2030"- an open and creative academic art and science community, inspiring cultural breakthroughs and creating value¹⁹.

The main public HMEIs in Portugal (such as Escola Superior de Música de Lisboa and Escola Superior de Música e Artes do Espetáculo) share a commitment to high-level artistic and technical training, while reflecting distinct institutional profiles. They promote artistic excellence, research, and cultural engagement, aiming to prepare students for professional activity in both national and international contexts. Some place particular emphasis on social responsibility, artistic experimentation, and community engagement, with a strong focus on developing critical, reflective professionals. Others highlight lifelong learning, diversity of musical genres and repertoires, innovation, and international collaboration, while also valuing the preservation of musical heritage. There are also institutions that combine artistic and technical education across multiple creative fields, encouraging interdisciplinary approaches aligned with the evolving demands of the cultural and creative industries²⁰.

The Hochschule für Musik und Theater "Felix Mendelssohn Bartholdy" Leipzig (HMT Leipzig) articulates its mission and vision through its commitment to excellence in

¹⁷ These descriptions are based on official mission statements and institutional texts available on their webpages.

¹⁸ <https://www.mdw.ac.at/1963/>, including an explicit Diversity Strategy. [accessed: 29.05.2025]

¹⁹ <https://lmta.lt/lt/apie-mus/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

²⁰ <https://cesem.fcsh.unl.pt/en/polo/polo-1-en/>, <https://www.esmae.ipp.pt/education/student-support-services#:~:text=We%20encourage%20the%20development%20of%20activities%20and,mission.%20This%20is%20where%20our%20focus%20is,> <https://www.esmae.ipp.pt/education/schools> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

artistic education, deeply rooted in the principles established by its founder, Felix Mendelssohn Bartholdy. The academy envisions an educational environment that integrates a wide range of practical and theoretical disciplines, fostering artistic excellence and innovation. Through curricular reforms and a commitment to comprehensive education, HMT Leipzig aims to develop well-rounded artists equipped to contribute meaningfully to the cultural landscape²¹.

The Conservatoire Royal de Bruxelles (CRB) is an historic institution dedicated to the highest level of artistic education in music and theatre. The Conservatoire aims to serve as a cultural hub of international scope, facilitating the exchange and transmission of knowledge and skills between students and practicing artist-teachers. It seeks to foster encounters, experimentation, and exchanges. The institution's cultural diversity serves as a source of development for students, shaping their personal and artistic identities²². In short, 'cultural diversity' as understood by the Conservatoire Royal de Bruxelles refers to the multiplicity of nationalities, artistic traditions and experiences present among students and staff, which is seen as a key factor enriching the educational process and the artistic development of students.

The Karol Lipiński Academy of Music in Wrocław is dedicated to serving both the public and the arts by advancing artistic concepts, conducting research and development in music, and providing top-quality education to music students. It aims to cultivate artists who, drawing from global musical achievements and respecting native cultural values, can develop their potential as artists, leaders, and citizens of both their homeland and the world. The Academy envisions itself as a leading institution in music education, committed to excellence and innovation. It strives to be a dynamic and inclusive community that nurtures artistic talent and contributes significantly to the cultural landscape, both nationally and internationally²³.

The Janáček Academy of Performing Arts (JAMU) in Brno, Czech Republic aims to cultivate artists who are both technically proficient and intellectually engaged, contributing to the The academy strives to be a hub for innovation in the performing arts, fostering an environment where students and faculty can engage in creative exploration and interdisciplinary collaboration. By maintaining strong ties with international partners and participating in global artistic networks, JAMU seeks to enhance its educational offerings and contribute meaningfully to the global arts community cultural landscape both within the Czech Republic and internationally²⁴.

The Jāzeps Vītols Latvian Academy of Music (JVLMA) in Riga, Latvia, aims to identify and cultivate new and enthusiastic musical talents, providing them with comprehensive education and opportunities to flourish. The academy brings together talented students, knowledgeable teachers, researchers, and supportive staff in a

²¹ <https://www.hmt-leipzig.de/hochschule/profil-leitbild> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

²² <https://www.conservatoire.be/en/the-conservatoire/missions/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

²³ <https://amuz.wroc.pl/misja-i-strategia-rozwoju-16> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

²⁴ <https://en.jamu.cz/about-us/our-mission/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

dynamic and innovative environment where creativity and experimentation are encouraged. The institution is committed to conducting research projects in the arts and sciences and to encouraging the artistic creativity of young musicians²⁵.

All institutions emphasize the provision of **high-quality, professional music education**. They strive to prepare students for careers as performers, educators, composers, or researchers. Each of the HMEIs aims to contribute to the **cultural life** of its country and beyond, seeing music not just as a discipline but as a societal and cultural force. There is a clear **international dimension** in each academy's mission or vision. Whether through partnerships, global engagement, or encouraging mobility, they aim to be part of the **global music community**. Most statements mention supporting **student development**, creativity, and self-realization, emphasizing individual artistic identity.

It is important to observe that certain institutions remain rooted in traditional frameworks. Although they articulate ambitions for increased international visibility, many continue to adhere to conventional academic models or are making only small modifications. In contrast, other institutions adopt a more interdisciplinary orientation, characterized by a commitment to artistic experimentation and research, and pursue modern, inclusive approaches that are strategically aligned with broader societal transformations and innovation across Higher Education.

5.5.2. ADVANCING GENDER EQUALITY IN HMEIs

This section explores how HMEIs are responding to the challenges presented by advancing gender equality in HMEIs through the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and related initiatives. By examining selected case studies, it highlights both the progress made and the gaps that remain in embedding gender equality into the institutional frameworks of European HMEIs.

In the context of HMEIs, gender inequality remains a persistent structural issue across Europe. Despite growing awareness of the importance of equality and diversity, this imbalance not only undermines principles of fairness and representation but also impedes the innovative capacity and societal relevance of these institutions.

As cultural and educational hubs, HMEIs have a critical responsibility to reflect and foster the values of inclusivity, justice, and equal opportunity. Diversity in terms of gender, ethnicity, socio-economic background, and ability must be seen not as peripheral considerations, but as foundational to academic excellence, sustainable development, meaningful artistic engagement, and the future of the field.

Structural discrimination and unequal access to education and academic careers not only hinder individual development, but also undermine the resilience, innovative capacity and social relevance of institutions dedicated to higher music education. A more diverse academic environment brings new perspectives, fosters creative

²⁵ <https://www.jvlma.lv/en/academy/about-jvlma> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

solutions, and encourages open dialogue that reflects the complexity of global challenges and moves beyond siloed working. Ensuring equality and embracing diversity must therefore be understood as key strategic priorities, to be actively promoted through clear and effective measures across the sector.

Attempts to ensure gender equality in HMEIs range from individual initiatives to formally approved GEPs. Below are some notable examples:

Academy of Performing Arts in Prague (HAMU) in the Czech Republic, has introduced a comprehensive Gender Equality Plan for a four-year period. This plan addresses key issues such as work-life balance, equal access to leadership positions, recruitment practices, and the prevention of gender-based violence. The institution has also established the role of an ombudsperson and conducts workshops on topics including safe academic environments and gender sensitivity²⁶.

The Sibelius Academy, University of the Arts Helsinki, in Finland, actively supports diversity and inclusion. It established a Gender Equality Working Group (DIGE) as part of the AEC. The DIGE group develops resources and conducts workshops to help institutions implement inclusive practices and promote gender equality in higher music education²⁷.

The Conservatory of Music Alessandro Scarlatti in Palermo hosted a workshop by the AEC DIGE Working Group focused on diversity, equity, and inclusion in higher music education. The institution has also developed regulations to support students with special needs and collaborates with international partners to promote inclusivity²⁸.

The Lithuanian Academy of Music and Theatre has implemented a Gender Equality Policy that emphasizes equal treatment in recruitment, promotion, and academic participation. It also addresses the prevention of discrimination based on gender, race, nationality, language, and other factors²⁹.

These examples reflect a commitment by European music institutions to fostering gender equality and inclusivity within their educational environments. Institutions are encouraged to adopt GEPs at the legal level; in some countries, having a GEP is a mandatory requirement for eligibility for research funding.

While most HMEIs in Europe are members of the AEC, which promotes gender equality and non-discrimination, GEPs are not yet universally adopted across all academies. This corresponds also to the current research framework in HMEI. The

²⁶ https://www.amu.cz/cs/veda-vyzkum-rozvoj/gender-equality-plan/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

²⁷ <https://www.uniarts.fi/en/documents/equality-and-diversity-plan-2021-2024/> <https://aec-music.eu/project/empowering-artists-as-makers-in-society/meet-the-aec-diversity-inclusion-and-gender-equality-dige-working-group>

²⁸ https://aec-music.eu/news-article/hme-institutions-from-sicily-gathered-in-palermo-for-an-interactive-workshop-on-diversity-equity-and-inclusion/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

²⁹ https://lmta.lt/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Equal-Policy_FEB14-002.pdf

advancement in the field of research would support the adaptation and application of GEP's.

The higher education system is also facing the challenges related to migration problems, both between European countries (e.g. immense number of Ukrainian refugees in countries like Poland, Germany) and from outside. This intertwining of cultural groups (unseen in modern history) with different backgrounds and needs, may redefine our understanding of the canon of repertoire, literature, and influence the curricula.

5.6. Rethinking Traditions of Historical Musicology in HMEIs

In the last few decades, historical musicology has gradually begun to respond to the postmodern changes that have reshaped the academic world. As part of this process, scholars have developed new approaches that aim to understand the present by critically examining it through a historical perspective and sought out new ways to situate themselves within changed funding and regulatory environments.

The concept of **decolonisation** has become a key framework for addressing longstanding structural inequalities. It calls for a critical reassessment of the systems and narratives that perpetuate **gender, ethnic, and racial disparities**, as well as **geopolitical imbalances**. In the context of musicology, it also highlights the dominance of a **canon centered on Western classical music**, often at the expense of other musical traditions.

While the term **decolonisation** may be resisted in certain contexts, its underlying objectives remain highly relevant. In HMEIs across Europe, efforts to decolonise curricula and institutional structures often confront deep-rooted legacies stemming from imperial expansion, nation-building processes of the 18th and 19th centuries, and in some regions, Soviet-era ideologies. These historical influences continue to shape the positioning of music institutions within national education systems, their internal hierarchies, faculty composition, teaching and research priorities, and their overall academic identity.

In light of this historical background, many contemporary challenges in HMEIs—including their position within education and cultural systems, institutional structures, faculty composition, and self-conception—can be traced directly to these historical imperial legacies. The traditional conservatory model, with its hierarchy of musical traditions privileging Western classical repertoire, frequently reflects colonial power structures that marginalised indigenous and non-Western musical practices. Faculty members in these institutions often perpetuate these hierarchies through curricula and pedagogical approaches that were shaped during periods of imperial cultural dominance. Post-imperial and post-Soviet influences remain particularly relevant in Central and Eastern European conservatories, where institutional reforms continue to grapple with these historical legacies.

In this context, if HMEIs wish to achieve greater academic and social relevance in today's European landscape, they must respond to the dynamics of change by integrating new intellectual paradigms, revising their curricular and institutional frameworks, and, where necessary, regularly updating their content. This is not a challenge exclusive to HMEIs but extends to higher education institutions across Europe. In the field of historical musicology, this means moving beyond traditional frameworks centred on the European canon, while maintaining respect for the European tradition and the disciplinary foundations of the field. The emerging field of Global Music History offers a promising exploratory framework by proposing a history of music rooted in global interconnectivity, cultural transfer, and plural historical experiences. European HMEIs should not uncritically adopt models developed in other non-European academic contexts, but should instead adapt and critically reflect upon such perspectives within European cultural and pedagogical realities. Doing so would create a dialogic space to facilitate the inclusion of historically marginalised repertoires and perspectives and reinforce musicology's role as a critical lens through which to explore colonialism, migration, and the global circulation of musical knowledge.

Efforts towards curricular decolonisation must be accompanied by a methodological shift: the revision of repertoires, the inclusion of non-Western sources and traditions, and the integration of decolonial, gender-based, and environmental approaches. Pedagogical practices should promote critical thinking, project-based learning, and meaningful engagement with the surrounding social environment. These reforms are not just about curriculum content, they represent a strategic commitment to reaffirming the academic legitimacy, epistemological diversity, and social engagement of HMEIs within 21st-century Europe.

Several ongoing examples illustrate the diversity of approaches to this issue:

Ukraine: The Tchaikovsky National Music Academy of Ukraine (formerly Kyiv Conservatory) has confronted decolonisation debates around the symbolic legacy of Tchaikovsky and the integration of Ukrainian musical traditions, particularly following the 2014 Revolution of Dignity and the 2022 Russian invasion. Faculty renewal remains an open challenge, particularly in overcoming entrenched Soviet pedagogical models.

Italy: The Conservatory of Music in Vicenza hosts the only formally structured Department of Ethnic Music in Italy, focusing particularly on Indian music and dance. It offers bachelor's and master's degrees in Traditional Music, helping expand the conservatory's offerings beyond the Western canon.

Türkiye: At Hacettepe University Ankara State Conservatory, the Department of Musicology (formerly Ethnomusicology) was renamed in an anti-colonial move to challenge the exoticisation implied by the "ethno-" prefix. This change coincided with curriculum reform integrating both art and traditional music.

Croatia: While Croatian musicologists are not institutionally limited to “Croatian topics,” national research infrastructures and paradigms still shape the scope of inquiry, often excluding the historical legacies of former Yugoslavia. A comprehensive decolonisation effort should include both Western and post-Soviet frameworks, as well as national and nationalistic limitations.

Germany: The Hochschule für Musik Weimar holds the only UNESCO Chair on Transcultural Music Studies in Europe (since 2016), with a strong focus on music’s cultural theory and anthropology.

These examples suggest that a broader, cross-European rethinking of tradition, nationalism, and colonial legacies is both possible and necessary. It is through such work that HMEIs can move towards becoming more inclusive, globally aware, and socially engaged institutions within the European research and education space. Historical musicology has a vital role to play in such a process.

5.7. Emerging Technologies & CCI

One of the most pressing challenges confronting all higher-education institutions, including HMEIs, involves adapting to and exploiting technological change.

The use of emerging technologies—whether based on artificial intelligence, digital processing, or other innovations—presents both significant opportunities and notable challenges. The key is to integrate these tools thoughtfully, not as replacements, but as a means of supporting and enhancing our work. Within HMEIs, there are numerous contexts in which such technologies can be effectively applied. This chapter does not seek to compile an exhaustive list of possible applications—given the rapid pace of technological development, such an attempt would be impractical. Instead, our aim is to illustrate the potential already being realized in many HMEIs around the world, and specifically in Europe.

Responding to new technologies and AI will require a different set of competences for young PhDs in musicology that also need to be proficient in data science disciplines to not miss employment possibilities. Whilst the landscape in universities is slowly shifting to give tools to students for, HMEIs are often focused on a more traditional approach of historical musicology. It is important to keep in mind the fair and care practices in use in musicology³⁰ and to integrate these in the curriculum, while also being able to train teachers and researchers to be at ease with these good practices.

HMEIs have opportunities for integrating AI into historical musicological research. Examples include: folklore/folk music archives, early fieldwork data of initial research dating back to the early 1900s, and early music manuscripts. All of these can become subjects of innovative research. In the case of early archives, artificial intelligence can

³⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/10698452> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

become a useful tool for reconstructing lost data (damaged manuscripts, vanished writings in music scores, long forgotten instruments, broken cylinders and vinyls for example.); it can, furthermore, provide detailed comparative analyses of historical musicological sources from different archives and non-compatible catalogues.

AI applications are already being used in HMEIs across Europe. As contextual examples, the Royal College of Music in Malaga uses AI - assisted composition; the Royal College of Music in the UK uses AI for avoiding injuries and burnout in the training of violinists. *Repertorium*³¹ uses AI to digitise manuscripts for historical musicologists and for research use; Optical Musical Recognition (OMR) and Music Information Retrieval (MIR) are used extensively. Sound Source Separation and Sound Field Reconstruction are specific AI Tools used by Repertorium in reconstructions of historical musicological research.

HMEIs are becoming spheres of experimentation and exploration of how artistic theory and practice interacts with technology, including with AI applications. This area of research is rife for collaboration with university departments in Computer Science, Psychology, Social Science, Heritage, Digital Media, CCI. The question needs to be asked; how can (historical) musicology inform and contribute to these developments?

AI is not only changing the way we interact with the world around us, it is creating new realities and worlds. It is therefore changing perceptions of, and access to, art, culture and creativity in particular. As with any new technologies, access, inclusivity and democratisation are and should be at the forefront of implementation. Technological innovation - or at least applications - in any case frequently break down boundaries to access.

HMEIs provide opportunities for collaboration not only with universities but also with commercial institutions, particularly within projects that bridge music, technology, and research. Such collaborations can serve as a foundation for creating innovative business ventures and fostering entrepreneurial initiatives in the cultural and creative industries. By combining artistic expertise with technological innovation, these partnerships contribute not only to academic advancement but also to broader economic development.

AI has a broader context within the opportunities for creative endeavour that new technologies offer. Some institutions have reorganised around new and innovative faculties, placing music—and historical musicology—into faculties of Creative Arts and Industries. Other, newer institutions, such as the University for the Creative Arts in the UK (established in 2005) have started afresh, with new technologies and research experimentation in digital media a core part of a new approach. Other institutions have evolved from roots in electronic music and electro-acoustic composition; Christ Church Canterbury University has musicologists working within a Faculty of Creative Arts and Industries; this is seen as an evolution from the electro-acoustic work of

³¹ www.repertorium.eu [accessed: 29.05.2025]

Daphne Oram³² and an association with the composer Peter Maxwell-Davies. The response of universities and HMEIs may differ, or may be utilised towards specific institutional strengths; equally, AI and new technologies may create better links as protocols for use in historical musicology and other music related fields become increasingly essential.

Projects using new technologies are often by their nature collaborative, and cross boundaries. The COVID-19 pandemic also normalised remote performances and ways of working; opportunities and challenges arose from this context.

It can be argued that the COVID-19 lockdowns served as a catalyst for the development and adoption of technological initiatives in HMEIs. For instance, at the Music Academy in Wrocław—as well as in many other Polish academies—education was conducted remotely during the pandemic, and elements of this mode of communication continue to be used today. This period also fostered creativity and led to the implementation of new solutions that have since become part of everyday academic and artistic practice.

A notable example is the *Poznań Laptop Orchestra*, established at the Academy of Music in Poznań during the COVID-19 lockdown period and continuing to be active today. The ensemble employs contemporary programming methods in its performances and comprises students of electroacoustic composition from the Academy of Music, as well as computer science students from the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań.

Historical musicology remains an important part of HMEIs, and musicologists affiliated with both of these Polish institutions often participate in interdisciplinary initiatives alongside scholars from the university sector.

A representative example of such interdisciplinarity is the ongoing project *Dziedzictwo muzyki polskiej*, coordinated by the Fryderyk Chopin Institute³³. Its aim is to expand digital access to Polish music from the 16th to the 19th century by creating an open, searchable online platform that integrates tools for musicological research, source analysis, and transcription. The project combines advanced technologies—including automated analysis and symbolic score encoding—with collaborative strategies such as crowdsourcing and partnerships with academic centres. Importantly, it engages researchers from both university departments and HMEIs, reflecting a broader trend toward integrated, technologically informed scholarship in the field of musicology.

³² <https://www.daphneoram.org/> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

³³ <https://portalmuzykipolskiej.pl/pl> [accessed 29.05.2025]

<https://www.gov.pl/web/popcwsparcie/dziedzictwo-muzyki-polskiej-w-otwartym-dostepie> [accessed 29.05.2025]

In the UK, the bUsRoUTes project³⁴ used game technology to create remote linked performances using MVN Animate software. This was combined with games engines such as Unity and Unreal. In one project, “Pepper’s Ghost”, ethnomusicological work was involved in using capture suits for performers of traditional Vietnamese instruments. The result was a live stream of the musicians, recorded live in Sweden, and translated into “ghosts”—skeletal figures—that appeared live on a stage in Folkestone, UK.

There is scope to see where staff in the field of historical musicology are innovating and exploring, and whether this is part of HMEI work, or an overlap with other staff projects and activities. Equally, this would be an area where we recommend that pump-priming funds are provided, across Europe, for innovative projects that provide scope for the development of best practice models that can be applied or utilised in the field of historical musicology.

6. Conclusion

This report highlights the complex and uneven landscape of historical musicology within European Higher Music Education Institutions (HMEIs). Whilst nearly all HMEIs across Europe include historical musicology in some form, its status, curricular integration, and research orientation vary significantly depending on national frameworks, institutional histories, and pedagogical models. The discipline’s presence ranges from departments with dedicated staff and research agendas to marginal inclusion within broader theory or performance-based curricula.

One of the key findings is the pronounced disparity in academic qualifications and professional recognition for historical musicologists within HMEIs. Requirements for teaching positions differ widely—from master’s degrees to PhDs with habilitation—reflecting national traditions rather than a unified European standard. Likewise, the capacity for career mobility between HMEIs and universities remains highly constrained in many contexts, limiting the development of hybrid academic-artistic profiles and hindering the circulation of knowledge across institutional boundaries.

The report also underscores the limited institutionalisation of research in many HMEIs. Whilst some institutions have developed strong models—such as dedicated research centres or integration of historical inquiry into historically informed performance practices—many others lack systematic research frameworks, often relying on individual initiatives rather than strategic institutional support. In some cases, historical musicology is considered secondary to performance training, which remains the core mission of most HMEIs.

Despite these challenges, the report identifies emerging opportunities. In several countries, reforms have begun to bridge the gap between HMEIs and universities,

³⁴ <https://www.routestock.org/post/busroutes> [accessed: 29.05.2025]

particularly through the creation of doctoral programmes, joint degrees, and increased access to research funding. Moreover, the growing recognition of artistic research opens new avenues for integrating scholarly and creative practices. Initiatives in inclusivity, gender equity, and decolonisation also suggest potential directions for renewing the mission and identity of HMEIs.

Overall, the report demonstrates the need for greater structural coherence, enhanced recognition of research within HMEIs, and sustained efforts to foster dialogue between performance and musicological scholarship. A lasting European mapping of historical musicology within HMEIs would provide a crucial foundation for this work and help articulate clearer institutional missions, career paths, and research strategies across the continent.